

THESIS PROPOSAL

**GENOMIC STUDIES OF PISCINE STREPTOCOCCI AND GENOME
ASSEMBLY OF CLARIIDAE CATFISHES (SILURIFORMES) FOR
AQUACULTURE ENHANCEMENT**

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**GRADUATE SCHOOL KASETSART UNIVERSITY
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Genomic studies of piscine streptococci and genome assembly of Clariidae catfishes (Siluriformes) for aquaculture enhancement

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GENOMIC STUDIES OF PISCINE STREPTOCOCCI AND GENOME ASSEMBLY OF CLARIID CATFISHES (SILURIFORMES) FOR AQUACULTURE ENHANCEMENT

INTRODUCTION

Global aquaculture is the process of farming aquatic organisms, both marine and freshwater, for human consumption and other uses, such as producing feed, pharmaceuticals, and related products. It represents the fastest-growing food production sector, providing over half of the seafood consumed globally, with Asia dominating production. In Thailand, inland aquaculture is critical for global food security, where freshwater species such as tilapia (*Oreochromis* spp.), catfish (*Clarias* spp., *Silurus* spp., and *Pangasius* spp.), and Asian seabass (*Lates calcarifer*) contribute significantly to domestic consumption and seafood exports (FAO, 2020; [Naylor et al., 2021](#)).

In 2022, aquaculture surpassed capture fisheries as the primary source of aquatic animals, producing 94.4 million tonnes compared to 92.3 million tonnes from wild-capture fisheries, [according to the Global Seafood Alliance](#). Globally, aquaculture production (including seaweeds) reached 130.9 million tonnes in 2022, valued at USD 313 billion, [according to the Food and Agriculture Organization](#). Major gains in aquaculture feed efficiency and fish nutrition have lowered the fish-in–fish-out ratio for many fed species, although dependence on marine ingredients persists and reliance on terrestrial ingredients has increased. To ensure sustainable growth, genetic improvement through selective breeding has become a key strategy, where optimizing traits such as growth, feed efficiency, sex determination, robustness, and disease resistance requires identifying and deploying relevant genetic variants.

Modern aquaculture breeding programs do not rely solely on conserving “pure” strains or extreme inbreeding. Instead, they are typically structured around families or lines that serve as a defined starting point and are improved cumulatively over gener-

ations. The goal is to increase the average performance of each new generation under farming conditions, while maintaining sufficient genetic diversity to avoid inbreeding depression and allow continued response to selection. Depending on production objectives, schemes may combine within-line selection, between-line divergence for specific traits, and controlled crossbreeding or hybridization to exploit heterosis or complementary traits. In this context, “elite” germplasm is not restricted to closed purebreds but includes any well-characterized line or composite background that delivers reliable genetic gain, robustness, and predictable performance in commercial systems.

Genomic tools have become central to designing and managing these breeding programs. Approaches such as genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS), genome-wide association studies (GWAS), and quantitative trait loci (QTL) mapping enable the identification of markers linked to growth, fillet yield, stress tolerance, and resistance to major pathogens ([Chaivichoo et al., 2023](#); [Lin et al., 2022](#)). Marker-assisted selection (MAS) and genomic selection then allow breeders to increase the frequency of beneficial alleles across cycles of selection, translating genomic information into measurable gains in production traits ([Yue, 2013](#)). However, the efficiency and reliability of all such efforts depend on high-quality, well-annotated genome assemblies to anchor trait-associated variants, resolve structural complexity, and support accurate estimation of relatedness and inbreeding ([Wang et al., 2015b](#)). Whole-genome resources also enable pathogen surveillance, vaccine target discovery, and integrated host–pathogen analyses.

In this thesis, I present the generation and analysis of genomic resources for two major aquaculture catfish species, *Clarias macrocephalus* and *C. gariepinus*, their F1 hybrid, and the bacterial pathogen *Streptococcus iniae*. Together, these datasets support data-driven selective breeding, rational vaccine development, and sustainable aquaculture practices in Thailand and beyond.

OBJECTIVES AND RATIONALE

Rationale

1. Catfish currently lack comprehensive genomic data to support selective breeding.
2. High-quality sequencing data are needed to support aquaculture development in Thailand.
3. *Streptococcus iniae* is a major pathogen of fish and catfish.
4. *S. iniae* lacks a Thai genome, blocking vaccine and antigen design.

General Objectives

1. To generate haplotype-resolved genomes for the family *Clariidae*.
2. To apply reverse vaccinology to *S. iniae*.

Specific Objectives

1. To sequence the Bighead Catfish (*C. macrocephalus*).
2. To sequence the F1 Hybrid catfish (*C. macrocephalus* x *C. gariepinus*).
3. To sequence pathogenic *S. iniae* isolated from diseased Asian seabass.
4. To apply Reverse Vaccinology and Quality-by-Design (QbD) frameworks to *S. iniae*.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Genomic Technologies for Aquaculture

1. Sequencing platforms (Illumina, ONT, HiFi)

Modern genome sequencing relies on breaking DNA into fragments and reconstructing the complete sequence computationally. These technologies are categorized as either short-read or long-read, based on the fragment length analyzed [Mahmoud et al. \(2023\)](#).

Figure 1 Long-reads vs Short-reads: Assembling a genome is like completing a jigsaw puzzle—fewer, larger pieces (long reads) are easier to assemble than many small pieces (short reads).
Credits: <https://nanoporetech.com/platform/technology>.

1.1 Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) Long-Read Sequencing

ONT sequences native DNA/RNA by passing strands through biological nanopores. Each base causes characteristic disruptions in ionic current that are decoded to reconstruct the sequence. Key advantages include ultra-long reads (>100 kb), direct detection of base modifications like methylation, and real-time sequencing. For aquaculture genomics, ONT reads span complex structural variations and repetitive elements previously unresolvable. Early ONT chemistries exhibited 15–20% error rates, but recent improvements have increased accuracy to nearly 99% ([Eisenstein, 2017](#)). In this

thesis, early ONT chemistry was used (approximately 20% error).

Figure 2 ONT sequencing

Credits: Nik Spencer/Nature

1.2 PacBio HiFi Long-Read Sequencing

HiFi sequencing employs Circular Consensus Sequencing (CCS), in which DNA polymerase makes multiple passes around circularized DNA fragments in Zero-Mode Waveguides (ZMWs). This generates consensus reads of 10–25 kb with 99% accuracy (Hon [et al.](#), 2020; Wenger [et al.](#), 2019). The combination of long reads and high accuracy allows HiFi to span repetitive regions while minimizing post-assembly error correction. HiFi assemblies often reach chromosome-scale contiguity with moderate

coverage (15–20 \times), enabling accurate variant discovery and QTL mapping for aquaculture breeding programs. The main limitations are higher DNA input requirements and cost compared to short reads, though reduced performance occurs in homopolymer regions (Mc Cartney *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 3 Flowchart of HiFi sequence read generation and downstream applications.

Credits: (Hon *et al.*, 2020)

1.3 Illumina Short-Read Paired-End Sequencing

Illumina sequencing uses Sequencing-by-Synthesis (SBS) chemistry to generate highly accurate short reads (100–300 bp) with >99.9% accuracy at massive scale and low cost. This makes it invaluable for error correction and SNP discovery in population genomics. However, short reads cannot resolve repetitive sequences exceeding read length, resulting in fragmented assemblies with gaps in complex, heterozygous genomes common in aquatic species. Most early fish genome drafts relied on Illumina due to availability and accuracy, but assemblies suffered from low contiguity and poor recovery of full-length genes.

Figure 4 Next-generation sequencing chemistry overview—Illumina NGS includes four steps: (A) library preparation, (B) cluster generation, (C) sequencing, and (D) alignment and analysis.

Credits: [An Introduction to Next-Generation Sequencing Technology](#)

2. Hi-C for Genome Scaffolding

Hi-C captures chromosome three-dimensional organization through proximity-ligation, where physically close DNA fragments become joined. Paired-end sequencing of these junctions reveals long-range linkage: contigs from the same chromosome show many Hi-C contacts while those from different chromosomes show few (Putnam *et al.*, 2016). This enables clustering, ordering, and orienting contigs into chromosome-scale scaffolds for **de novo assembly**—construction without a reference genome—rather than **reference-guided assembly** which requires an existing genome.

Hi-C has become essential for achieving chromosome-level assemblies in aquaculture species, enabling precise localization of genes and QTLs for breeding traits. In polyploid fish genomes, Hi-C correctly separates duplicated loci and provides insights into 3D genome structure, chromatin conformation, and regulatory interactions (Dudchenko *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 5 Ultra-long-range sequencing for genome scaffolding

Credits: Ultra-long-range Sequencing for Genome Scaffolding

3. Haplogenome Assembly of Catfish Genomes

Haplogenome assembly reconstructs each parental haplotype independently instead of producing a collapsed consensus sequence. This captures the full spectrum of

allelic and structural variation, valuable for outbred species and highly heterozygous organisms such as interspecific catfish hybrids. By resolving phase-specific sequences, haplotype assemblies reveal allele-specific expression patterns critical for understanding gene function and optimizing selective breeding. The approach typically uses long-read sequencing (PacBio HiFi or ONT) with bioinformatic phasing to separate maternal and paternal haplotypes. A well-known example includes the assembly of haplotypes in interspecific Eucalyptus hybrids, analogous to the genome-wide structural differences observed between *Silurus asotus* and *S. meridionalis* that are linked to hybrid traits [Chen et al. \(2021a\)](#). Similarly, in catfishes, haplotype assemblies of *Clarias macrocephalus*, *C. gariepinus*, and their F1 hybrids enable precise characterization of chromosomal rearrangements, gene duplications, and introgression events—laying the foundation for genomic selection and improved aquaculture productivity [Duong and Scribner \(2018\)](#).

4. In Summary

These sequencing platforms capture genome structure and identify variants—SNPs¹, indels², and structural variants (SVs)³—associated with economically important traits ([Chaivichoo et al., 2020](#)). Short reads excel at accurate SNP/indel detection, long reads resolve structural variants and complex regions, while Hi-C provides chromosomal-level scaffolding. As of May 2025, NCBI hosts over 3.01 million genomes including 51,820 eukaryotic genomes, with fewer than 500 being haplotype-resolved, complete vertebrate genomes (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/genome/>).

¹Single-base changes at specific genomic positions, used as genetic markers.

²Short insertions or deletions of 1–50 bp.

³Large genomic alterations >50 bp including deletions, insertions, duplications, inversions, and translocations.

Clarias Catfish Aquaculture in Southeast Asia

1. Evolutionary History and Distribution

Catfish (Siluriformes) are widely cultivated freshwater species crucial for food production across Africa, the Americas, and Asia (Lisachov *et al.*, 2023). This diverse order diverged during the early Cretaceous (145 Ma) and comprises over 36 families and 3,000 species (Ferraris, 2007). While distributed globally in freshwater environments with some marine extensions, catfish are most diverse in tropical South America, Asia, and Africa. Key representatives like *Clarias* and *Ictalurus* serve as both research models and economically valuable aquaculture species.

2. Classification and Biology

Bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*) and North African catfish (*C. gariepinus*) belong to family Clariidae, order Siluriformes. These air-breathing catfish are economically important in Southeast Asia and Africa, respectively. *C. macrocephalus*, native to Southeast Asia and widely farmed in Thailand, has a broad flattened head, short barbels, and reaches 40–50 cm. Its body is dark brown to black with pale blotches. *C. gariepinus*, introduced globally for its fast growth and environmental tolerance, grows to 1.7 m with an elongated body and long dorsal fins. It survives oxygen-depleted waters using its suprabranchial organ for atmospheric breathing.

Figure 6 Left: Female *C. macrocephalus* (Credits: Matillano, J.D.). Right: *C. gariepinus* (Credits: Larsen, J.H.)

F1 hybrids from *C. gariepinus* males × *C. macrocephalus* females combine parental advantages: body form from *C. macrocephalus* with rapid growth from *C. gariepinus*. Both species thrive at 26–32°C.

3. Role in Food Production and Economy

Clarias species are extensively farmed across Asia and Africa. *C. macrocephalus* is primarily used for hybrid production with *C. gariepinus* (Lisachov [et al.](#), 2023; Nanakorn [et al.](#), 2004), yielding sterile F1 hybrids with hybrid vigor (heterosis) that combine rapid growth and desirable body characteristics. However, hybrid sterility necessitates separate parental production systems. The lack of high-quality reference genomes limits implementation of modern breeding tools like ddRAD sequencing, low-coverage genome sequencing, and CRISPR/Cas9. Studies indicate low introgression risk in *C. macrocephalus*, supporting potential genetic improvement efforts.

Case Study: Genome Assembly Applications in Tilapia

Tilapia (*Oreochromis* spp.) exemplifies successful genomic applications in aquaculture (Yu [et al.](#), 2022). Researchers identified adaptive responses⁴ to salinity stress through genome-wide SNP analysis linked to osmoregulation and survival (Gu [et al.](#), 2018; Jiang [et al.](#), 2019; Rengmark [et al.](#), 2007). Key tolerance genes include *prolactin* (PRL) (Breves [et al.](#), 2013), *growth hormone* (GH1) (Deane and Woo, 2008), *insulin-like growth factor 1* (IGF1) (Yan [et al.](#), 2020), and *plasma-membrane Ca²⁺-ATPases* (PMCA) (Rengmark [et al.](#), 2007). Similar studies in rainbow trout (Le Bras [et al.](#), 2011), Atlantic salmon (Norman [et al.](#), 2012), and stickleback (Kusakabe [et al.](#), 2016) collectively established foundations for marker-assisted selection (MAS) in aquaculture. Non-synonymous mutations in salt regulation genes enhance tolerance and alter phenotypes. These achievements required high-quality reference genome assemblies.

⁴Biological adjustments to environmental stress through gene regulation, metabolic changes, or immune modulation.

GENOME ASSEMBLY – BIGHEAD CATFISH

Overview of Genome Assembly Strategy

The haplotype-resolved genome of *Clarias macrocephalus* was assembled using an hybrid sequencing strategy comprising four DNA sequencing platforms generating various types of DNA reads (i.e., in DNA sequencing, a read is an inferred sequence of base pairs (or base pair probabilities) corresponding to all or part of a single DNA fragment). The four DNA sequencing technologies used to read the gDNA of bighead catfish into DNA reads (short-reads and long-reads) were: PacBio HiFi CSS ([Wenger et al., 2019](#)) (Circular consensus sequencing⁵, long-reads of base accuracy 99.9%), used for maximizing genome assembly quality. Oxford Nanopore (ONT) noisy 1D long-reads (20%.err)⁶ ([Jain et al., 2018b](#)) for increasing assembly continuity and to span complex repeat regions of the genome. Proximity-ligation (Hi-C) ([Dudchenko et al., 2017](#); [Putnam et al., 2016](#)) data for long-range linking information to phase (i.e., the specific arrangement of alleles on the same chromosome to distinguish maternal and paternal haplotypes) and scaffold contigs (i.e., separating haplotypes). These complementary data types facilitated haplotype resolution and scaffold anchoring and allow to generate dual assemblies⁷ from a single diploid tissue. Among the tested assemblers (Hifiasm ([Cheng et al., 2021](#)), Flye ([Kolmogorov et al., 2020](#)), wtdbg2 ([Ruan and Li, 2019](#))), I selected Hifiasm for the haplotype-resolved assembly because of its ability to separate parental haplotypes (phasing) on low genome coverage (< 13X) HiFi data. In contrast I found that Flye and wtdbg2 produced collapsed consensus assemblies. Below, I outline the main steps for the complete genome assembly of bighead catfish Haplotype 1 and Haplotype 2.

⁵Circular consensus sequencing (CCS) is a high-accuracy long-read sequencing method, commonly used with PacBio HiFi reads, where multiple passes of the same DNA molecule are combined to generate a consensus sequence.

⁶Oxford Nanopore 1D reads are single-strand long reads that historically exhibit high error rates, often around 10–20%, due to insertions, deletions, and base-calling inaccuracies. These reads are valuable for spanning long genomic regions but require polishing for accuracy.

⁷Dual assemblies refer to separate genome assemblies generated for each haplotype in a diploid organism, allowing resolution of heterozygous regions and structural differences between homologous chromosomes.

1. **Genomic DNA Sequencing, Genome Survey, and k -mer Meryl Databases** Genomic DNA was extracted from the liver tissue of a single male bighead catfish individual using a custom protocol (Supikamolseni [et al.](#), 2015). Sex was determined based on histology and external gonadal examination (Kitano [et al.](#), 2007; Wyneken [et al.](#), 2007). Sequencing was performed using four complementary platforms generating four synergistic raw sequencing data types: (i) Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) High-Fidelity (HiFi) sequencing (Wenger [et al.](#), 2019) for generating highly accurate contigs, (ii) Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) long-read sequencing (Jain [et al.](#), 2018b) for scaffolding and resolving repetitive regions, and (iii and iv) Illumina short-read 150 base paired-end sequencing (Hi-C, and standard non Hi-C) (Bentley [et al.](#), 2008) for chromosomal phasing and error correction, respectively. Genome survey aims in assessing genome characteristics (genome size, heterozygosity, repeat content) from raw sequencing data (e.g., Illumina short-reads) using k -mer analysis in Jellyfish (Marçais and Kingsford, 2011) and GenomeScope2.0 (Ranallo-Benavidez [et al.](#), 2020). Meryl databases (N=2) for 21-mer and 31-mer (bighead.hifi.illuminaPCRfree.gt1.db.meryl) hybrid k -mer databases, made from combined Illumina and HiFi reads using Meryl (Rhie [et al.](#), 2020), as explained in the T2T-polish GitHub repository (<https://github.com/arangrhie/T2T-Polish>) (Rhie [et al.](#), 2022). K -mer Meryl databases use 21-mer and 31-mer DNA strings to support quality evaluation and error correction in genome assemblies. The shorter 21-mer spectra provide high sensitivity for detecting potential errors, while the longer 31-mer spectra offer higher specificity, validating true variants and minimizing false positives. During genome polishing, these k -mer databases enhance effective coverage in low-depth HiFi regions by leveraging k -mer spectra to guide targeted corrections and improve assembly accuracy.
2. **Initial Assembly Generation (Contigging and Phasing):** Contigging is the process of assembling overlapping DNA reads into continuous sequences without gaps (i.e., contigs). These contigs are then separated and assigned to a phase group using proximity-ligation data (Hi-C) based on their parental origin and spatial physical distance in the cell nucleus. Therefore, a contig that comes from a

haplotype is referred to as a haplotig⁸, and in a diploid phased assembly there are two groups of homologous haplotigs (i.e., unitigs, one per haploid "homotype" haplotype). Here, Hifiasm was used in "Hi-C UL" mode (Cheng et al., 2021) to generate a haplotype-resolved assembly using Hi-C + ONT + HiFi reads (Figure 8D, left), followed by GreenHill (Ouchi et al., 2023) using all data types: Hi-C + Illumina + ONT + HiFi reads for further scaffolding and phasing of the haplotigs (Figure 8E), and finally wtdbg2 (Hu et al., 2024; Ruan and Li, 2019) was employed with HiFi and Illumina short-reads correcting small errors at the nucleotide level (i.e., SNPs) while preventing switch errors (i.e., allele switching between homologous haplotypes). This produced two phased contig sets representing homologous haplotypes (Figure 9).

3. **Hi-C Scaffolding and Their Validation:** Scaffolds are computationally ordered and oriented arrays of contigs that have sequence gaps along their length. The process of scaffolding of contigs is about arranging and orienting contigs into larger structures, sometimes with gaps, using additional data like proximity ligation (Hi-C) in order to reconstruct an in-silico equivalent to the karyotype (referred to as "Scaffotype") which consists of Hi-C scaffolds of "pseudochromosomes" (i.e., chromosome pseudomolecules), visualized as Hi-C maps. Prior to Hi-C scaffolding, it is possible to break the contigs at erroneous sites, for that, misassembly corrections are done using CRAQ (Li et al., 2023), then Hi-C scaffolds (i.e., contigs and scaffolds) are flipped, reoriented, and refined to improve structural accuracy, this step is known as the "manual review step"⁹ and is performed using JBAT (JuiceBox Assembly Tools) (Dudchenko et al., 2017), next, a "post-review step"¹⁰ step seals contigs (i.e., by creating gaps between newly adjacent contigs and inserting 500 'N' characters to represent unknown

⁸In an unphased assembly, a contig may join alleles from different parental haplotypes in a diploid or polyploid genome (see (Lewin et al., 2019) and <https://lh3.github.io/2021/04/17/concepts-in-phased-assemblies>). The process of separating sequences based on their parental haplotype in diploid genomes is referred to as "haplotype phasing".

⁹In Hi-C scaffolding, manual review involves visually inspecting contact maps (e.g., using Juicebox or HiGlass) to detect misassemblies, orientation errors, or misplaced contigs that automated tools may miss.

¹⁰Post-review refers to the stage after Hi-C contact map inspection, where validated corrections (e.g., flips, cuts, or joins) are applied to the genome assembly.

sequences) to form Hi-C scaffolds to ultimately reconstruct pseudochromosomes followed by **3D-DNA "post-review"** validation (Dudchenko [et al.](#), 2017) (Figure 8F). Finally more gaps were closed with TGS-GapCloser (Xu [et al.](#), 2020) (Figure 8G). These steps — including CRAQ break detection, Hi-C read alignment, manual review in JBAT, and post-review in the 3D-DNA pipeline — were iteratively performed three times. As illustrated in Figure 8F, this cycle can be repeated if needed after contig polishing (Figure 8H), and typically results in well-defined Hi-C scaffolded pseudochromosomes (Figure 8C).

4. **Assembly Polishing of Contigs and Benchmarking:** Polishing a genome assembly consist in correcting sequencing errors using additional data (Meryl k -mer databases, long-reads and short-reads). To further improve assembly accuracy, reads were aligned to the polished assembly, the three primary long-read mappers employed were Winnowmap (Jain [et al.](#), 2022), Minimap2 (Li, 2018), and VerityMap (Mikheenko [et al.](#), 2020) (previously known as TandemTools), these were used in assembly validation only (i.e., not for variant calls and genome polishing). Secondary alignments (i.e., reads flagged with bit 0x100¹¹), low-quality regions (i.e., MAPQ¹² = 0), and hard-clipped reads (i.e., alignments with hard clipping operations indicated by 'H' in the CIGAR string¹³) were excluded from analysis using samtools (Li and Durbin, 2009). This read realignment step was crucial for validating assembly completeness and reducing errors. Non-haplotype-aware tools¹⁴ (e.g., Racon (Vaser [et al.](#), 2017), Clair3 (Zheng [et al.](#), 2022)) were applied cautiously to minimize errors from parental haplotype switches, while Merfin (Formenti [et al.](#), 2022) filtered edits for polishing and BCFtools consensus produced the final polished sequence. For large variants and closing gaps using read alignments I used Sniffles2 (Smolka [et al.](#), 2024) for **large structural**

¹¹In SAM/BAM flags, bit 0x100 indicates a *secondary alignment*. Tools like Picard use this flag to mark reads that are not the primary alignment of a read with multiple mappings.

¹²MAPQ (Mapping Quality) is a Phred-scaled score that reflects the confidence in the read's alignment position. Higher values indicate more reliable mappings.

¹³The CIGAR (Compact Idiosyncratic Gapped Alignment Report) string encodes how a read aligns to a reference, using operations such as matches (M), insertions (I), deletions (D), soft clips (S), and others. For example, 100M indicates 100 matching bases.

¹⁴Non-haplotype-aware tools do not distinguish between maternal and paternal sequences in diploid or polyploid genomes, often collapsing allelic variants into a single consensus sequence and potentially masking structural differences between haplotypes.

variant (SV) calling, specifically for insertions (INS) and deletions (DEL). I evaluate genome quality in term of errors found in the assembly that are not found in raw reads, for that I calculate the Quality Value, usually referred to as QV¹⁵ of a genome assembly where QV refers to the Phred quality score (or quality (Q) score), an integer representing the estimated probability of an error (i.e., that a base is incorrect). The polishing workflow implemented here for correcting big-head catfish ensured high nucleotide accuracy Quality Values (QV) (from initial QV33 to around QV46) after Benchmarking against recommended assembly metrics, from the VGP paper (Rhie et al., 2021).

Figure 7 Representative specimens of the bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*), collected for high-quality haplotype-resolved genome assembly. The individuals were reared under controlled aquaculture conditions prior to tissue sampling. *C. macrocephalus* is an economically important freshwater species native to Southeast Asia, widely cultured in Thailand for selective breeding and genomic improvement programs.

Methodological details are presented in the following sections and in Figure 8.

¹⁵Quality Value (QV) is a Phred-scaled score used to represent base-level or assembly-level accuracy. If P is the probability of error, then $Q = -10 \log_{10}(P)$, or equivalently, $P = 10^{-Q/10}$. Higher QV indicates greater accuracy.

Figure 8 Comprehensive haplotype-resolved genome assembly and scaffolding workflow for bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*). **(A)** Hi-C contact map (Juicebox v2.16.0). **(B)** Genome assembly using PacBio HiFi, ONT, and Hi-C reads with Hifiasm (Hi-C UL mode) and Flye for consensus. **(C)** Hi-C scaffolding via GreenHill and 3D-DNA. **(D)** Manual post-review with JBAT. **(E)** Gap filling using TGS-GapCloser and QuarTeT GapFiller. **(F)** Genome polishing with NextPolish2 and CRAQ. **(G)** Assembly QV validation with Merqury, Pilon, BCFtools, and VerityMap. **(H)** Mitochondrial genome assembly with MitoHiFi and Minimap2. The pipeline yields two high-quality phased haplotype assemblies representing the complete bighead catfish genome.

Haplotype Resolution, Hi-C Scaffolding, and Phasing

The haplotype-resolved diploid assembly of bighead catfish combined HiFi, ONT, and Hi-C data using Hifiasm¹⁶ (`--hic --hifi --ul --primary`) (Cheng et al., 2022) v0.19.8-r603, resulting in two Hi-C-phased contig sets (.hic.hap1 and .hic.hap2), representing two separate and complete haploid homologous haplotypes (Cheng et al., 2021). To scaffold Haplotype 1 and Haplotype 2 with long reads (HiFi and ONT), proximity-ligation (Hi-C), and Illumina paired-end short reads, I used GreenHill¹⁷ (`-cph $hap1 $hap2 -p $combined_ont_hifi -IP1 -IP2 -HIC`) (Ouchi et al., 2023) v1.0.0.

1. Hi-C Mapping and Manual Review

To build heatmaps of Hi-C contacts between pair of loci and obtain Hi-C scaffolds (post haplotype resolved assembly), I used the Juicer pipeline (`--assembly -S early`) (Durand et al., 2016) v2.17.00 and for detecting chromatin loops in Hi-C data I used Hi-CCUPS (CPU mode)¹⁸ (`--ignore-sparse -cpu`) v2.17.00, which aligned Hi-C reads the sequence data to GreenHill scaffolds and assign a mapping quality score using BWA-MEM (Li and Durbin, 2010) v0.7.17_r1188. PCR duplicates¹⁹ and near duplicate mapped reads were removed using samtools (Li and Durbin, 2009) v1.18. Hi-C contacts²⁰ were generated at various resolutions (2.5 Mb to 5 kb) for computing the bins of the Hi-C heatmaps. Visualization of Hi-C maps was performed using the script `run-assembly-visualizer.sh` from the 3D-DNA pipeline (Dudchenko et al., 2017) v02/12/2018. To manually review Hi-C scaffolds for misjoins or errors,

¹⁶Hifiasm is a genome assembler designed for PacBio HiFi reads. It constructs phased assembly graphs to generate haplotype-resolved contigs for diploid or polyploid genomes (Cheng et al., 2021).

¹⁷GreenHill is a scaffolding tool that integrates contigs from Hifiasm with multiple types of sequencing data (e.g., Hi-C, long reads, short reads) to produce chromosome-scale genome assemblies.

¹⁸The CPU mode of Hi-CCUPS enables loop calling using only CPU resources, avoiding GPU acceleration. This mode is useful on systems without compatible GPUs but may run slower. The `--ignore-sparse` option skips sparse matrix optimization, which may improve detection in low-coverage or fragmented assemblies but increases memory usage.

¹⁹PCR duplicates are multiple reads originating from the same original DNA fragment, introduced during PCR amplification. They can bias downstream analyses and are often removed during preprocessing.

²⁰Hi-C contacts represent physical interactions between chromatin regions captured via proximity ligation. In genome assembly, they are used to infer the spatial organization of contigs and scaffold them into chromosomes.

Juicebox Assembly Tools (JBAT) ([Durand et al., 2016](#)) v2.16.00 was used, and regions with misjoins or under-collapsed heterozygosity²¹ were edited based on off-diagonal signals in the Hi-C read density heatmap, indicating contig/scaffolding errors. Post-review validation of Hi-C scaffolds was performed using "3D-DNA-post-review.sh" v180114 ('--sort-output -c 27'), a module of the 3D-DNA pipeline ([Dudchenko et al., 2017](#)). Unplaced scaffolds (i.e., sequences that could not be confidently assigned to any specific chromosome) remain outside the main chromosomal assembly and were filtered out by FASTA file manipulation in SeqKit ('--by-length -reverse -m 2,500,000') ([Shen et al., 2016](#)) v2.7.0, resulting in 27 chromosome-length scaffolds per haplotype.

²¹Under-collapsed heterozygosity occurs when highly divergent alleles are mistakenly assembled as separate contigs or scaffolds, leading to duplication of regions that should be collapsed into a single representation.

Figure 9 Post-Hifiasm HiC UL assembly genome Bandage graphs - Haplotype 1 and Haplotype 2. **(A)** Bandage graph after Hifiasm Hi-C UL assembly of Haplotype 1 (.hic.hap1.p_ctg.gfa). **(B)** Bandage graph after Hifiasm Hi-C UL assembly of Haplotype 2 (.hic.hap2.p_ctg.gfa)

2. Genome Polishing with NextPolish2

With the goal of increasing assembly quality QV values and correcting small SV errors (SNV/indels), I generated a HiFi mapping file after counting repetitive k -mers in reads with Meryl ($k=15$)²² for Winnowmap, a version of minimap2 optimized for read alignment in repetitive regions which leverages a bloom filter²³ to filter alignments based on k -mer multiplicity²⁴ (Jain et al., 2020, 2022). Next I generated two k -mer databases (21-mer and 31-mer files) from trimmed short-reads using the Yak k -mer analyzer (<https://github.com/lh3/yak>). The Winnowmap mapping file—in BAM format (a binary compressed version of SAM for storing aligned reads)—the target assembly—in FASTA format (a plain-text representation of nucleotide sequences)—and the two parental databases—in YAK format (k -mer frequency tables)—were used as input for genome polishing with NextPolish2 v0.2.0 (Hu et al., 2024).

3. Gap Filling via Genus Alignment

To resolve assembly gaps—i.e., regions consisting of 'NNN' between contigs within scaffolds (also referred to as pseudochromosomes)—homologous sequence information and read-based polishing were applied (Lischer and Shimizu, 2017). For this purpose, additional scaffold sets were generated using Hifiasm ('--primary') as contigger, by varying the type of read data input (HiFi, ONT, Hi-C) and the haplotype purging options²⁵ ('-10'). Additionally, orthologous sequences (i.e., DNA se-

²²Repetitive k -mers are short DNA sequences of length k that occur multiple times in the reads. Using Meryl with $k = 15$, such repetitive k -mers can be counted and analyzed to identify low-complexity or highly duplicated regions, which may complicate assembly or mapping.

²³A Bloom filter is a space-efficient probabilistic data structure used to test whether an element is a member of a set. It allows for fast membership queries with a small false positive rate and is commonly used in genomics for k -mer filtering and sequence indexing.

²⁴ k -mer multiplicity refers to the number of times a specific k -length sequence appears in a set of reads or a genome. It is used to estimate coverage, detect repeats, and assess genome characteristics such as heterozygosity and ploidy.

²⁵In Hifiasm, the '-l' option controls haplotig purging levels: '0' disables purging, '1' removes only contained haplotigs, '2' purges all haplotig types, and '3' applies the most aggressive purging (default for non-trio assemblies). Trio-binned runs default to '-l0', and allow only '-l0' or '-l1':contentReference[oaicite:1]index=1.

quences originating from a different species) were retrieved from NCBI Datasets²⁶ for species in the family Clariidae (Taxonomy ID: 13012, n = 3 reference sequences): *C. fuscus* (GCA_030347435.1), *C. gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2), and *Channallabes apus* (GCA_030522415.1), last accessed February 2024. Three rounds of TGS-GapCloser (Xu et al., 2020) v1.2.1, followed by one round of QuarTeT GapFiller Lin et al. (2023) v1.2.1 were used on Haplotype 1, Haplotype 2. The first round used filtered high quality HiFi reads (Q20, length over 10 kb) to fill medium sized gaps (over 20,000 bases). The second round used filtered ONT reads (Q25, length over 10 kb) to fill larger gaps (over 20,000 bases), while the third round used polished unitigs (.p_utg.fa) of Hifi-asm assembly. Gaps were reduced from n = 4015 (Haplotype 2) to n = 2501 (Haplotype 2) to n = 1100 (Haplotype 2) after TGS-GapCloser. Finally, all reference genomes and scaffold sets (p_utg) were used as combined input and gaps were reduced to n = 550 (Haplotype 2) after QuarTeT GapFiller ('default parameters -q *.fa') (Lin et al., 2023) v1.2.1.

4. Final Polishing with Pilon

To enhance the accuracy and quality values (QV) of the haplotype assemblies of *C. macrocephalus* and to precisely polish the genome assembly while correcting error-prone regions, I performed a *k*-mer analysis, read alignments, and sequence polishing using Pilon (Walker et al., 2014) v1.24.

1. **Identification of missing reads at assembly seqmers error positions:** Positions of erroneous *k*-mers of non-repetitive *k*-mers found in the genome (i.e., the error seqmers) were identified with Merqury (Rhie et al., 2020) and Meryl (Rhie et al., 2020), as explained in the T2T-Polish GitHub workflow (“QV estimate with hybrid *k*-mer db”; <https://github.com/arangrhie/T2T-Polish>). *k*-mers were counted using Meryl ('meryl count k=\$k') for each haplotype assembly, and a combined (hybrid) 21-mers from Illumina and HiFi data Meryl *k*-mer database

²⁶NCBI Datasets is a resource provided by the National Center for Biotechnology Information that allows users to programmatically access and download genome, gene, and protein data in standardized formats for bioinformatic analysis.

was created through union-summing (`'meryl union-sum'`). I further filtered the k -mers from the hybrid read database, retaining only those k -mers with higher multiplicity values, such as greater than 5 or 10 (`'meryl greater-than'`), to eliminate low-confidence sequences. Next, the k -mers unique to the reads and absent from the assemblies were isolated using Meryl's difference operation (`'meryl difference'`). These read-only k -mers represented genomic variation not captured in the assemblies. I used these filtered k -mers to extract reads containing these unique sequences from both the Illumina and HiFi datasets using the lookup command (`'meryl-lookup'`).

2. **Mapping of reads:** I started with high-quality sequencing reads. ONT reads were filtered using NanoFilt [De Coster and Rademakers \(2023\)](#); [De Coster et al. \(2018\)](#) v2.8.0 to remove low-quality bases, while for Illumina paired-end reads (R1 and R2, representing the forward and reverse reads), I removed low-quality sequences and DNA adapter sequences²⁷ using Fastp (`'-5 -3 -n 0 -f 5 -F 5 -t 5 -T 5 -q 20'`) ([Chen et al., 2018](#)) v0.23.4. Next, HiFi reads were aligned the combined haplotype assemblies using Winnowmap aligner (`'-W repetitive_k15.txt'`) based on k -mers found in repeats. For ONT reads, I used minimap2 (`'map-ont'`) without secondary alignments (`'--secondary=no'`) and alignments were filtered at MAPQ > 30 (`'-q 30'`). Illumina short-reads were aligned using Bowtie2 ([Langmead and Salzberg, 2012](#)) Reads were aligned using Bowtie2 in *end-to-end sensitive mode* (`--sensitive`) to reduce spurious alignments. The options `--no-mixed` and `--no-discordant` excluded improperly paired reads—`--no-mixed` filters out pairs where only one read aligns, while `--no-discordant` removes pairs with unexpected orientation or spacing. Only alignments within the expected *insert size* (i.e., the genomic distance between the start of the forward read and the end of the reverse read) were retained, with a threshold of $500 \text{ bp} + 2 \times \text{read length}$ to account for Illumina paired-end sequencing. Finally, PCR duplicates were removed using SAMtools (`markdup`).

²⁷DNA adapter sequences are short synthetic oligonucleotides ligated to DNA fragments during library preparation for sequencing. They enable amplification, barcoding, and binding to the sequencing platform but must be removed during preprocessing to avoid interference with read alignment.

3. **Running pilon and calling the consensus:** Pilon was employed on assemblies for correcting SNPs, INDELs (i.e., 1-2 base insertions and deletions), and other base-level errors. In individual haplotypes, each scaffold was processed by Pilon with parameters (`'--genome, --frags, --bam, --targets, --fix all, --vcf, --diploid, --minmq 30, --minqual 30'`) to use the alignments from all data types (HiFi, ONT, and short reads). The output Variant Calling Files (VCF) of containing the detected variants were sorted by position using (`'bcftools sort'`), compressed using `bgzip`, and indexed using (`bcftools index`)²⁸, and final consensus sequences were generated for each scaffold using (`'bcftools consensus -f $genome.fa -H 1'`).

The overall median quality value metric increased from 41 to approximately 45-47 after haplotype-aware targeted assembly polishing.

5. Hi-C Scaffolding with HapHiC

To reintegrate unplaced scaffolds in each haplotype in the pseudochromosomes, I used Quartet and HapHiC. First, I aligned the unplaced contigs to reference genome *C. fuscus* (GCA_030347435.1), and reference genome *C. gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2) using Quartet AssemblyMapper (Lin et al., 2023) v1.2.1 with the following parameters (`'-r $reference -q $contigs -c 50000 -l 2000 -i 90 -a minimap2'`). I identified 53 MB and 33 MB of unplaced scaffold sequences in bighead catfish Haplotype 1 and Haplotype 2, respectively, with strong homology to *C. fuscus* pseudochromosomes, next I filtered bighead catfish Haplotype 1 and Haplotype 2 separately with SeqKit (Shen et al., 2016) v0.8.1 to retain pseudochromosomes and concatenated them to unplaced scaffolds. For the preparation of Hi-C scaffolding step, Hi-C reads were mapped to separate haplotypes using BWA-MEM (`'-5SP'`) after making a BWT index²⁹

²⁸`bcftools index` creates a compressed index (`.csi` or `.tbi`) for VCF or BCF files, allowing rapid random access to variants by genomic position during downstream processing or visualization.

²⁹The *BWT index* refers to a data structure derived from the *Burrows-Wheeler Transform (BWT)*, which allows fast and memory-efficient alignment of sequencing reads to a reference genome. It compresses the genome while retaining the ability to search for exact or approximate matches, enabling tools like Bowtie2 and BWA to align short reads with high performance.

for Haplotype 1 and Haplotype 2 (`'bwa index $genome.fasta'`) and Hi-C read alignments filtered for PCR duplicates³⁰ and secondary alignments (`'samblaster $BAM | samtools view --@ $threads -S -h -b -F 3340'`) using the software Samblaster (Faust and Hall, 2014) v0.1.26. Hi-C scaffolding was performed on bighead catfish haplotypes using HapHic (Zeng et al., 2024) v1.0. The resulting Hi-C maps were visualized in JBAT and using (`'haphic plot'`) for separate scaffolds from each haplotype (Figure 16 and Figure 17) but also with all scaffolds represented in a wide-map (Figure 18), and a post-review of the Hi-C scaffold was performed as described in the previous section. Finally, three rounds of TGS-GapCloser followed by one round of targeted Pilon polishing specifying the new targets resulted in a genome of global higher quality (i.e., both in term of QV quality values and CRAQ's metrics of CRE/CSE structural accuracy). I addressed the duplication errors³¹ visible in the heterozygous peak of the k -mer coverage (i.e., from the Merqury spectra CN) with more or less success by using haplotype-specific k -mer databases. This involved applying (`'meryl difference'`) command to identify erroneous k -mers and using (`'meryl-lookup'`) command to extract reads associated with these k -mers. Finally, I used BCFtools to call a consensus³² using the opposite haplotype (`'-H 1'`) within `bcftools consensus` command, effectively reversing most haplotype switch errors.

6. SV and SNP Consensus Polishing

Consensus polishing³³ was automated by following instructions from the T2T-polish GitHub repository (<https://github.com/arangrhie/T2T-Polish>). A HiFi mapping file of repetitive k -mers ($k=15$) was generated with Meryl and used in Winnowmap for

³⁰PCR duplicates refer to read pairs that originate from the same DNA fragment and are amplified multiple times during library preparation, potentially leading to biased coverage if not removed.

³¹Duplication errors refer to the erroneous presence of redundant sequences in genome assemblies, often caused by uncollapsed haplotypes, repetitive regions, or misassemblies. These can inflate genome size and complicate downstream analyses.

³²Calling a consensus in `bcftools` refers to generating a modified reference sequence by applying variant calls (e.g., from a `.vcf` file) to a reference genome, resulting in a consensus sequence that reflects the sample's specific genotype.

³³Consensus polishing is the process of correcting errors in a draft genome assembly using aligned reads, typically by averaging observed base calls at each position in a read pileup. Most polishing tools are not haplotype-aware and must be run on both haplotypes together, meaning reads are distributed across haplotigs without distinguishing parental origin. This can lead to miscorrections in heterozygous regions.

HiFi read alignment (`'-MD -W .repetitive_k15.txt -ax map-pb'`), followed by alignment filtering with samtools (`'-Sb'`). pb-falconc filtered hard-clipped reads and for bit 0x104 in Picard³⁴ (`'bam-filter-clipped -t -F 0x104 --output-count-fn'`) (<https://github.com/bio-nim/pb-falconc>) v1.15.0 was then used to filter clipped reads. Genome polishing was performed using the liftover branch of the Racon GitHub repository, using Racon with (`'-L -S'`) options (Vaser et al., 2017) v1.5.0. After polishing, the k -mers present in the genome (seqmers) were counted using Meryl count ($k=21$). Merfin was then applied using (`'-readmers Illumina.HiFi.gt1.PCRfree.hybrid.meryl-seqmers'`) and the hybrid- k mer db of reads to evaluate the results by comparing the distributions in the reads and in the polished genome (Formenti et al., 2022; Rhie et al., 2022). For consensus generation (i.e., to apply polishing edits to the genome assembly), I used BCFtools (`'-H 1'`) for two rounds of genome correction. Assembly quality metrics were measured for QV, completeness and BUSCOs scores, I found a large increase in QV in most chromosomes (min. increase $> +1-5$ QV points) after ONT Racon and Merfin, the median QV was 50, the progress over months is presented in Figure 10.

³⁴The SAM flag 0x104 is a combination of 0x004 (read unmapped) and 0x100 (not primary alignment). It indicates that the read is both unmapped and not the primary alignment, typically seen in secondary alignments of unaligned reads or ambiguous multi-mappings.

(A) Bighead catfish assembly (after post-review)

Figure 10 Bighead Catfish Assembly Status January 2024 - November 2025. **(A)** Haplotype 1 (blue) and Haplotype 2 (purple) ideograms showing gaps on pseudochromosomes (orange rectangles) and telomeres (blue triangles) after manual-review in Juicebox (JBAT). **(B)** Same assemblies a few months later.

7. Mitochondrial Genome Assembly

The mitochondrial genome (mtDNA) was assembled by mapping to reference (NC_046749.1) bighead catfish mtDNA, available at NCBI Nucleotide³⁵. Minimap2 ('-ax map-ont --secondary=no') mapped nanopore reads to the reference and minimap2 ('-ax sr') mapped Illumina reads. PCR duplicates in short reads were removed from the alignments using samtools markdup and the results were visualized in the Integrative Genome Viewer (IGV) (Thorvaldsdottir *et al.*, 2012). Pilon ('--fix all --diploid --changes --vcf --tracks --minmq 10') was used to correct mtDNA (NC_046749.1) and call SNPs, SVs, gaps and local variants and obtain the consensus mtDNA sequence. Reads were re-aligned to the consensus mtDNA sequence and no more SNPs were visible in the IGV. Next, mapped reads were filtered with samtools view ('-F4 -q 20') and re-assembled *de novo* with Unicycler (Wick *et al.*, 2017) for comparison. The results were visualized in Bandage-ng (Wick *et al.*, 2015) v2022.09. The assembly was polished with Pilon and the two homologous mitochondria were compared using minimap2 ('--eqx -x asm5'). Gene annotations were generated using MitoFinder (Allio *et al.*, 2020) v1.4.2. To ensure that the mitochondrial genome was correct and not dissimilar to other mtDNAs in Siluriformes, I downloaded all reference mtDNA sequences for (N = 209) species of Siluriformes catfish from NCBI Nucleotide, last accessed September 2024. All sequences were taken from NCBI RefSeq³⁶ and not from NCBI GenBank³⁷. All mtDNA nucleotide sequences (N = 210) were renamed to the Pan-SN naming scheme (<https://github.com/pangenome/PanSN-spec>), concatenated in a single multi-FASTA including the bighead catfish mtDNA generated here after Pilon, and all-versus-all alignments were performed with wfmash, then ODGI was used to filter the alignment graph, and visualizations were made with Bandage and multiQC (Ewels *et al.*, 2016). All tools of the pipeline were part of the larger PGGB (Pan Genome Graph Builder) (Guarracino *et al.*, 2022). The results of the alignments are shown in Figure 11, the mtDNA aligns well with other sequences in the phylogenetic order and is not an outlier.

³⁵NCBI Nucleotide is a public database providing access to sequences from GenBank and RefSeq.

³⁶NCBI RefSeq is a curated, non-redundant database of genomic, transcript, and protein sequences.

³⁷NCBI GenBank is a comprehensive archive of nucleotide sequences submitted by researchers.

Figure 11 All-versus-all 2D representations of mitochondrial DNA sequences alignments in Siluriformes catfishes. The mtDNA assembled for bighead catfish is on the last row (blue color).

8. Transposable Element Annotation

Two complementary approaches were used to identify transposable elements (TEs)³⁸ in the bighead catfish genome. **(1)** A species-specific TE library was generated *de novo* for the bighead catfish. **(2)** A curated fish TE library was retrieved from the FishTEDB database (<https://www.fishtedb.com/>) and used as a reference for cross-species TE annotation.

8.1 De novo transposable element library for bighead catfish

De novo TE annotation was performed using EDTA (Extensive de novo TE Annotator) (Ou *et al.*, 2019) v2.2.0. The pipeline integrates several tools to detect different element types. LTR harvest (Ellinghaus *et al.*, 2008) v1.5.10 identifies LTR retrotransposons by efficiently locating structural features such as border positions, LTR lengths, and motifs in large genomic datasets. LTR FINDER (Xu and Wang, 2007) and the parallel version of LTR FINDER (Ou and Jiang, 2019) v1.1.0 accelerate LTR detection using parallel computing for large genomes. LTR retriever (Ou and Jiang, 2017) v2.9.0 refines LTR annotations to improve accuracy and remove false positives. TESorter is an accurate and fast way to classify LTR retrotransposons (Zhang *et al.*, 2022) v1.4.7, GRF (Generic Repeat Finder) (Shi and Liang, 2019) v1.1 for genome-wide *de novo* repeat detection. TIR-Learner (Su *et al.*, 2019) v1.1.2 uses machine learning to detect terminal inverted repeat (TIR) transposons, including miniature inverted TEs (MITEs). HelitronScanner (Xiong *et al.*, 2014) v1.0 identifies Helitrons by recognizing their characteristic structural motifs. RepeatModeler (Flynn *et al.*, 2020) v2.0.3 performs *de novo* repeat discovery and builds a comprehensive repeat library. MAFFT (Kato and Standley, 2013) v7.526 is used for multiple sequence alignments, and HMMER (Finn *et al.*, 2011) v3.4 is used for domain-based searching and TE classification.

³⁸Transposable elements (TEs), also known as “jumping genes,” are mobile DNA sequences that can move or replicate within the genome. They play key roles in genome evolution, structural variation, and gene regulation.

8.2 FishTEDB general fish-specific TE library collection

Next, libraries of TE consensus sequences³⁹ for transposons were retrieved from the FishTEDB database (Shao *et al.*, 2018) version 1, which contains different species of fish and their associated transposable element libraries in `.fasta` file format, and these sequences were merged with EDTA's *de novo* bighead catfish initial TE annotations. To reduce the library complexity and to create a non-redundant TE library (i.e., to lower the number of sequences and redundancy of the combined TE library dataset), I used CD-HIT-EST (`'-d 20 -aS 0.95 -c 0.95 -G 0 -g 1 -b 500'`) (Li and Godzik, 2006) for an 80% identity threshold and 80% alignment coverage of TE sequences in all-against-all sequence clustering following the commonly used 80%-80% rule (Goubert *et al.*, 2022). The reduced TE library was used to mask (i.e., to annotate) the bighead catfish genome for TEs with RepeatMasker (Smit, AFA, Hubley, R. & Green, P RepeatMasker at <http://www.repeatmasker.org>).

³⁹TE (transposable element) consensus sequences are artificial, representative sequences constructed by aligning and averaging multiple genomic copies of a TE family. They do not correspond to any specific real insertion, but serve as idealized references for annotation and classification.

GENOME ASSEMBLY – F1 HYBRID CATFISH

Overview of Genome Assembly Strategy

Starting from an **F1 hybrid catfish** (i.e., a first filial generation catfish made from the cross of a pure bighead catfish and a pure North African catfish), I reconstructed two complete haploid, non-homotypic parental genomes, comprising 27 pseudochromosomes for *C. macrocephalus* and 28 for *C. gariepinus* (Fig. 25). In most F1 hybrids derived from divergent parental species, the observed heterozygosity rate—typically around 10%—reflects the inter-specific genomic divergence between the two haploid sub-genomes, encompassing both single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and structural variants (SVs). The complete workflow for generating chromosome-scale assemblies of the Thai F1 hybrid catfish is presented in Figure 12. The workflow consists of six sequential steps (from **Step 1A** to **Step 6**) that integrate multiple sequencing technologies and analysis tools and pipelines in specific order used to achieve optimal phasing and Hi-C scaffolding at a high-contiguity, low structural error rate, high solve rates, and high base-accuracy genome assemblies in highly heterozygous F1 genomes. Below, I outline each step in detail.

- **Step 1: Genomic DNA Sequencing, Genome Survey, and Meryl Databases**

Genomic DNA was extracted from the liver tissue of a single F1 hybrid individual using a custom protocol (Supikamolseni *et al.*, 2015). Sex was determined to be female based on histology and external gonadal examination (Kitano *et al.*, 2007; Wyneken *et al.*, 2007). Sequencing was performed using four complementary platforms generating four synergistic raw sequencing data types: **(i)** Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) High-Fidelity (HiFi) sequencing (Wenger *et al.*, 2019) for generating highly accurate contigs, **(ii)** Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) long-read sequencing (Jain *et al.*, 2018b) for scaffolding and resolving repetitive regions, and **(iii and iv)** Illumina short-read 150 base paired-end sequencing (Hi-C, and standard non Hi-C) (Bentley *et al.*, 2008) for chromoso-

mal phasing and error correction, respectively. Genome survey aims in assessing genome characteristics (genome size, heterozygosity, repeat content) from raw sequencing data (e.g., Illumina short-reads) using k -mer analysis in Jellyfish (Marçais and Kingsford, 2011) and GenomeScope2.0 (Ranallo-Benavidez et al., 2020). Raw sequencing reads quality was assessed FastQC (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>) v0.1.12 for short reads and using NanoPlot v1.42.0 for long reads. Meryl databases (N = 2) consisted in 21-mer and 31-mer (hybrid.hifi.illuminaPCRfree.gt1.db.meryl) hybrid k -mer databases, made from combined Illumina and HiFi reads using Meryl (Rhie et al., 2020), as explained in the T2T-polish GitHub repository (<https://github.com/arangrhie/T2T-Polish>) (Rhie et al., 2022). k -mer Meryl databases use 21-mer and 31-mer DNA strings to support quality evaluation and error correction in genome assemblies. The shorter 21-mer spectra provide high sensitivity for detecting potential errors, while the longer 31-mer spectra offer higher specificity, validating true variants and minimizing false positives. During genome polishing, these k -mer databases enhance effective coverage in low-depth HiFi regions by leveraging k -mer spectra to guide targeted corrections and improve assembly accuracy.

- **Step 2: Contig Assembly and Their Haplotype Phasing** Contig assembly was performed using Hifiasm (Cheng et al., 2021), a haplotype-resolved assembler integrating data from HiFi reads, Hi-C reads, and ONT reads. This resulted in two haplotype-separated sub-genomes⁴⁰ (*hap1* and *hap2*). However, I observed that the Hifiasm algorithm artificially de-duplicated the primary phased haplotype assembly, producing two redundant copies, namely `.hic.hap1.p_ctg.fa` and `.hic.hap2.p_ctg.fa` which were nearly identical (combined genome size of 3.6 Gb versus expected 1.8 Gb, GenomeScope2.0). The best strategy was therefore to cluster parental haplotigs (i.e., the haplotype-specific contigs also referred to as "unitigs", contained in the haplotype-resolved polished unitig graph without

⁴⁰In the context of an F1 hybrid, a subgenome refers to the haploid genome inherited from one parent species. Since diploid hybrids carry one genome copy from each parent, they contain two sub-genomes—each representing a distinct parental lineage.

small bubbles) prior to performing additional scaffolding and phasing. After, Hifiasm, the initial genome graph in .gfa file format was fragmented, containing over 1661 polished unitigs (P_utg.gfa). To resolve these issues, I used polished unitigs instead of primary contigs as input for HapHiC (Zeng et al., 2024). In brief, to prepare for HapHiC, *in situ* Hi-C data was aligned to the Hifiasm draft genome assembly (P_utg.gfa) using BWA aligner designed for Hi-C data (i.e., setting '5SP'), results were Hi-C read alignments in SAM file format (Li et al., 2009), these were pre-filtered to allow a mapping quality of 1 (MAPQ1) (i.e., for the best Hi-C match only) with Samtools view (Danecek et al., 2021) and with a maximum of two mutations allowed per Hi-C read alignment (i.e., edit distance⁴¹ NM =< 2) with Samblaster (Faust and Hall, 2014). HapHiC was used to error-correct, anchor, order and orient the pieces in the Hifiasm polished unitig assembly. The HapHiC method performs an initial clustering of unitigs based on their haplotype assignment in Hifiasm. Settings were set to ('--remove_allelic_links 2') to account for genome diploidy, and "nchrs" set to ('55') for 55 chromosomes as the expected karyotype (Maneechot et al., 2016). Results of combining Hifiasm Hi-C and HapHiC for the highly heterozygous (10% heterozygosity, GenomeScope2.0 in Fig. 30) F1 genome were a successfully scaffolded and phased unitig assembly on the first attempt, reduced the number of gaps and increased solve rate and resulted in very high assembly quality metrics and success, achieving intermediate results of > 99.2% *k*-mer completeness, 55 scaffolds (i.e., pseudochromosomes), > 97% BUSCO completeness, an our expected genome size of 1.8 Gb, and only 1–2 switch errors after assembly quality assessment with Inspector (Chen et al., 2021b) v1.3.

- **Step 3: Hi-C Scaffold Pseudo-molecules Processing and Their Validation**

Initially, chromosome-scale assemblies were not processed and validated using CRAQ (Li et al., 2023), a software which identifies large-scale structural errors

⁴¹Edit distance refers to the number of nucleotide differences between a read and the reference sequence. For example, NM:i:1 means 1 mutation, and NM:i:2 means 2 differences (substitutions, insertions, or deletions).

(i.e., false inversions⁴², false translocations⁴³) within pseudochromosomes, finds breakpoints in the problematic contigs, and split at misassembly junctions prior performing pseudo-molecule construction and manual refinement (i.e., manual-review). I directly used Hifiasm output for Hi-C scaffolding and manual review of Hi-C scaffolds in Juicebox Assembly Tools aka JBAT / Juicebox (Dudchenko et al., 2017; Durand et al., 2016). Juicebox was used for manual Hi-C scaffold review, resolution of misjoins and structural artifacts. For more information on the manual-review in JBAT, please see the DNA Zoo Genome Assembly Cookbook (<https://www.dnazoo.org/methods>). In brief, HapHiC generated .assembly and .hic data files for visualization and manual curation of Hi-C scaffolds in Juicebox, these files were automatically created using the 3D-DNA visualization module, in conjunction with Juicer Tools, which resulted in .hic contact maps for the draft and the final genome assemblies. As a rule, apart from the initial HapHiC which used .gfa from Hifiasm, I always used CRAQ prior for FASTA assembly correction prior to manual review step using JBAT, which was employed to polish the genome assembly output by HapHiC and further polishing steps.

- **Step 4: Structural and Base-Level Polishing** In several cases the many different types of draft assemblies were used as the starting point to improve gaps, structure and contiguity of the "HapHiC" F1 hybrid catfish assembly. These were both originating from the same assembly data (GreenHill, Flye, Hifiasm), or eventually from reference genomes of *Clarias gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2) and *C. macrocephalus* (unpublished) which were also used for comparative analysis, aiding in structural validation. Additional assembly was performed through Flye (HiFi mode) (Kolmogorov et al., 2020) and GreenHill (Ouchi et al., 2023). Haplotype-specific contigs (.hic.hap1.p_ctg.fa and .hic.hap2.p_ctg.fa from Hifiasm ('--primary')) were scaffolded all together by using GreenHill, from Hi-C + Illumina + HiFi + ONT reads and Flye to generate extra solutions to

⁴²False inversions are incorrectly inferred inversion events in genome assemblies or alignments, often caused by misassemblies, poor-quality mapping, or structural variation artifacts. They may appear as reversed segments but do not reflect true biological inversions.

⁴³False translocations are apparent inter-chromosomal rearrangements that arise from assembly errors or misalignments rather than real biological events. They can result from chimeric contigs, repetitive sequences, or incorrect scaffolding.

better resolve structural variations, gaps, and highly repetitive elements such as satellite DNA⁴⁴. Large structural variants were corrected using Unimap (Li, 2018) (Unimap, available at <https://github.com/lh3/unimap>) and Sniffles2 (Smolka et al., 2024), identifying and resolving insertions, deletions, and rearrangements. Base-level polishing was performed iteratively using Clair3 (Zheng et al., 2022) for small variant correction and Merfin (Formenti et al., 2022) for error filtering, ensuring high-confidence base calls⁴⁵ and correcting sequencing errors.

- **Step 5: Final Genome Refinement and Quality Assessment** Final quality assessment included quality values (QV) estimated using Merqury (Rhie et al., 2020), with QV scores calculated at a k -mer size of $k=21$ and $k=31$ from their respective 21-mer and 31-mer hybrid k -mer databases, BUSCO (Simão et al., 2015) v5 was used to assess gene completeness with the Actinopterygii_odb10⁴⁶ database. Inspector software (Chen et al., 2021b) v1.3 estimated base-level accuracy and error rates using read pileups⁴⁷. The final curated genome achieved **QV60+** with 99,4% k -mer completeness, structured into chromosome-scale scaffolds comprising 55 pseudochromosomes.
- **The Mitochondrial Genome:** It was assembled by mapping ONT read data and Illumina data (as PacBio HiFi reads are less effective at capturing circular genomes due to adapter binding limitations) to reference mtDNA (NC_046749.1) from bighead catfish, available at NCBI Nucleotide.

⁴⁴Satellite DNA consists of highly repetitive, non-coding sequences arranged in tandem arrays, often in blocks of 200 bases. These repeats may contain minor mutations and are typically located in centromeric or pericentromeric regions, contributing to chromosome structure and function.

⁴⁵In the context of polishing with a VCF file, base calls refer to the consensus nucleotides supported by the read alignments at each genomic position. These calls are used to correct the draft assembly, replacing bases where variant evidence (e.g., SNPs or indels) is strong and consistent.

⁴⁶Actinopterygii_odb10 is a lineage-specific BUSCO dataset from OrthoDB version 10, containing a curated set of conserved single-copy orthologs for ray-finned fishes (Actinopterygii). It is used to assess the completeness of genome assemblies and annotations in this clade.

⁴⁷Read pileups are stacks of sequencing reads aligned to the same genomic region, used to visualize and quantify base-level support across positions. They form the basis for calling variants or consensus bases in polishing and variant detection workflows.

Figure 12 Workflow for Genome Assembly and Quality Assessment of the F1 Hybrid Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* × *C. macrocephalus*). This figure outlines the complete workflow for assembling the F1 hybrid catfish genome, highlighting the progenitor species (*C. gariepinus* and *C. macrocephalus*), and quality metrics achieved at each key assembly steps.

1. Assembly Review and Comments

1.1 For Comparative Genomics

Gene annotations (exons/coding-sequences (CDS)⁴⁸) were transferred from *C. gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.1) to both catfish sub-genomes using Liftoff [Shumate and Salzberg \(2021\)](#) (minimap2-based, 85% coverage - identity). Orthologous gene clusters (Orthogroups) were first identified using the software OrthoFinder ('`orthofinder -f /proteomes -M msa -a 126 -t 126`') ([Emms and Kelly, 2019](#)) v.2.5.5. Subsequently, I utilized rbhXpress (<https://github.com/SamiLhll/rbhXpress>) and macrosyntR ([El Hilali and Copley, 2023](#)) v0.2.19 to analyze the resulting orthogroups and visualize their syntenic relationships⁴⁹ across species.

1.2 Iterative Polishing of the Hybrid Catfish Genome

The assembly curation process extended over six months, with extensive manual review of alignments using Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV). The curated assembly exhibits minimal conflicts with raw sequencing data and contains no known misjoins. This manual intervention proved essential to overcome limitations of automated variant callers, which frequently fail to distinguish true genomic variations from allelic differences—a challenge that persists even when employing specialized correction tools such as Merqury ([Rhie et al., 2020](#)) and Merfin ([Formenti et al., 2022](#)).

Despite employing identical assembly pipelines for both subgenomes in the F1 hybrid, the bighead catfish subgenome demonstrated slightly lower nucleotide quality, likely attributable to increased repeat complexity—a characteristic assembly challenge in teleost genomes. Heterozygosity analyses of pure-bred individuals revealed

⁴⁸Exons are regions of a gene that remain in the mature mRNA after splicing. Coding sequences (CDS) are the portions of exons that are translated into protein. Not all exons contain CDS, as some may be untranslated (UTRs).

⁴⁹Syntenic relationships refer to the conservation of gene order and orientation between regions of different genomes. They indicate shared ancestry and are used to compare genome structure, detect rearrangements, and infer evolutionary events.

that *C. macrocephalus* exhibits lower heterozygosity (0.62%) compared to *C. gariepinus* (1.0%) (Figure 30). The final assembly achieved high quality values (QV) at both $k=21$ and $k=31$, with robust completeness metrics including CRAQ structural accuracy. The combination of manual curation, iterative polishing, and uniform read coverage proved critical for overcoming inherent limitations in both software algorithms and sequencing depth. The final assembly comprises 55 pseudochromosomes, accurately representing both parental haplotypes from a single F1 individual.

During initial assembly, optimal results were achieved by generating multiple independent assemblies from the same dataset followed by post-hoc merging and scaffolding. Specifically, combining outputs from Flye and GreenHill with Hifiasm improved resolution of complex genomic regions. Under conditions of limited read depth, Hifiasm occasionally exhibited problematic behavior, extending reads and switching to longer overlapping reads despite significant nucleotide differences (>20 SNPs)—a level of variation inconsistent with sequencing error alone. Additionally, using related reference genomes to fill assembly gaps requires careful validation, as incorrect placements frequently outnumber accurate ones without manual verification. Hi-C scaffolding underwent three rounds of manual review using Juicebox, involving contig splitting at off-diagonal signals and identification of scaffold gaps, ultimately reducing contig count from $>2,000$ to <500 .

1.3 Telomeric Refinement and Structural Improvements

Telomeric sequence refinement represented a significant technical achievement. Manual extension of clipped sequences at chromosome termini successfully incorporated five additional telomeric regions containing canonical $[\text{TTAGGG}]_n$ motifs. While telomeres may not be essential for most genomic analyses, their accurate representation enables precise chromosome boundary delineation. Notable improvements included:

- *C. gariepinus* chromosome 16: left telomeric repeat count increased from 138 to

1,602

- *C. gariepinus* chromosome 18: left telomeric repeat count increased from 268 to 1,411
- *C. macrocephalus* chromosome 7: left telomeric repeat count increased from 199 to 924

These refinements increased the number of pseudochromosomes with bilateral telomeres from 43 to 48, while reducing those with unilateral telomeres from 8 to 7. Telomeric additions contributed approximately 400 kb to the total assembly length, representing substantial progress toward telomere-to-telomere (T2T) completeness for multiple chromosomes.

Subgenomic analysis revealed additional differences between parental haplotypes, including heterozygosity rate variations and assembly complexity differences attributable to limited nanopore coverage. While most genomic gaps have been resolved, centromeric and satellite regions remain challenging, particularly where HiFi read coverage is absent or where only MAPQ0 Illumina reads provide support, necessitating reliance on lower-accuracy ONT data.

1.4 Quality Value Enhancement Through Manual and Automated Polishing

The polishing strategy combined automated QV correction with manual curation. Initial variant calling with Clair3 identified over 60,000 variants, subsequently resolved using Merfin. Despite achieving QV60 at $k=21$, a final manual curation round introduced 8,410 edits, including 551 large structural variants, resulting in QV improvement of 1–5 points. The complete manual curation process comprised four distinct rounds:

Round 1: Sniffles2 identified 755 target regions across all alignment files for manual review.

Round 2: Cross-assembly curation using Unimap examined scaffolds from Flye, GreenHill, and Hifiasm P-contigs, incorporating seqmer error files. This resulted in 2,221 manual edits and application of 5,951 variants.

Round 3: Combined Winnowmap and Unimap alignments enabled identification of 8,710 variants from 5,740 alignments, with 1,932 applied to the assembly. Additionally, 300 gaps were resolved following Sniffles2 and BCFtools consensus-based corrections.

Round 4: Correction of 97 large structural variants, including 10 visible only through VerityMap alignments. To ensure genome reliability, 65 gaps were introduced to mask sequences lacking proper read support or exhibiting high error profiles.

Post-masking, 247 structural variants (196 insertions, 73 deletions) identified using Sniffles2 were applied to the genome. These variants, derived from ONT pb-falconc-filtered alignments (<https://github.com/bio-nim/pb-falconc>) realigned at Hifiasm contig boundaries with 50 nt margins, were approximately 90% homozygous and 10% heterozygous. Genomic error k -mers showed non-uniform chromosomal distribution, clustering in regions with ONT-only or single-depth coverage (511 loci total). Further correction using Clair3 (Zheng et al., 2022) addressed 22,625 ONT-based consensus errors and 7,558 HiFi Winnowmap variants, achieving median QV31.

Assembly validation using IGV demonstrated quality improvements and structural resolution. Chromosome 03 showed clear reduction in k -mer error rates and increased QV post-polishing. Chromosome 02 analysis revealed a false duplication present in Hifiasm but absent in Flye, confirmed by doubled homozygous coverage and lack of supporting HiFi alignments. A single spanning ONT read and clipped Illumina read validated boundary precision. Consistent single-nucleotide markers across all data types (HiFi, ONT, Flye) suggest potential for further refinement using high-confidence variants (AF > 0.9) with Clair3 (Zheng et al., 2022) and WhatsHap (Martin et al., 2016).

Figure 13 Quality value and coverage validation using Integrative Genomics Viewer. (A) Chromosome 03 demonstrating QV improvement following polishing procedures. (B) Chromosome 02 showing false duplication and gap analysis through comparative assembly assessment.

Following eight months of genome curation, the estimated QV improved from Q40 to Q60, demonstrating that F1 hybrid genomes can achieve superior nucleotide-level accuracy compared to single-species assemblies. For comparison, the pure-breed bighead catfish assembly achieved median QV40–50 ($k=21$, $k=31$, pileup), while the current F1 hybrid genome demonstrates ten-fold higher accuracy using comparable sequencing coverage, analytical tools, and curation effort.

Figure 14 F1 Hybrid Catfish Assembly status January 2024 - November 2024.

VALIDATION OF CATFISH ASSEMBLIES

Benchmarking Methodology

This chapter presents the results and technical validations performed on the genome assemblies of the two catfish species. First, I present the most common metrics to measure the quality and completeness of the assemblies, next I present each individual assembly with results, finally comparative genomic analysis are provided and illustrate how these two genomes can be used for comparative studies across species. Metrics of continuity, structural accuracy, base accuracy, and functional completeness were used for benchmarking as described in the Vertebrate Genome Project (VGP) paper ([Rhie et al., 2021](#)).

1. Metrics Assessed

1.1 Continuity and summary statistics

To assess continuity and summary statistics of the assembly, I compute the following measures for scaffold/contig (N50, N90, NG50, LG50, and LG90)⁵⁰ with RagTag (`ragtag.py asmstats -g`) ([Alonge et al., 2022](#)) v2.1.0.

1.2 Repeat completeness and continuity of repeats

To measure repeat completeness and continuity of repeats for assessing assembly quality, I estimated the percentage of fully assembled LTR retroelements (LTR-RTs)⁵¹ and computed the long terminal repeat (LTR) Assembly Index (LAI) using two

⁵⁰N50 and N90 represent the contig or scaffold length such that 50% or 90% of the total assembly length is contained in contigs/scaffolds of that length or longer. NG50 is similar to N50 but calculated relative to an expected reference genome size. LG50 and LG90 indicate the minimum number of contigs or scaffolds whose combined length makes up 50% or 90% of the assembly, respectively.

⁵¹LTR-RTs (Long Terminal Repeat Retrotransposons) are a class of transposable elements characterized by direct long terminal repeats at both ends. They replicate via an RNA intermediate and reverse transcription, and are major contributors to genome size and structure in many eukaryotic organisms.

reference-free programs, LTR Assembly Index (LAI) (Ou et al., 2018) and LTR_retriever (Ou and Jiang, 2017) v2.9.00. To assess the assembly quality of complex repeats (centromeres), I used TandemTools and TandemQUAST (Mikheenko et al., 2020) v1. Telomere prediction for the presence / absence and orientation of telomeres was done with TIDK, a Telomere Identification Toolkit Brown et al. (2023), implemented in TeloExplorer ('-m 50 -c animal'), a module of QuarTeT Lin et al. (2023). To estimate gaps, I used the script detgaps, available on GitHub (<https://github.com/dfguan/asset>).

1.3 Structural accuracy (regional and structural errors and reliable blocks)

To assess structural accuracy I used the CRAQ software ('sms_coverage=5 ngs_coverage=20 -B T --minimap2-sensitve')(Li et al., 2023) v1.0.9, more specifically ('-q 20 -m 2 -f 0.4 -h 0.6 -r 0.75 -a 20'). CRAQ is a method for assembly structural validation relying on the study of mapped reads, clipped reads and coverage support by two or more simultaneous sequencing platforms to find supporting regions or reliable blocks (Rhie et al., 2021).and visualized results using the Integrative Genome Viewer (IGV) (Thorvaldsdottir et al., 2012). CRAQ evaluates genome assembly quality based on clipped-read evidence from both short and long reads. It reports two main types of errors:

1. **Clip-based Regional Errors (CREs)**, which represent small-scale local misassemblies identified by short-read clipping without structural disruption.
2. **Clip-based Structural Errors (CSEs)**, which represent large-scale misassemblies supported by long-read clipping near breakpoint regions.

These errors are quantified into two sub-scores: **R-AQI** (based on CREs) and **S-AQI** (based on CSEs). Both scores contribute to the global **Assembly Quality Index (AQI)**, ranging from 0–100, where higher values indicate better assembly integrity. AQI is computed based on error density relative to genome size.

1.4 Cross-species structural correctness

To assess cross-species structural correctness, I used the same references from related catfish species for one-to-one nucleotide-level alignments of orthologous segments with MashMap2⁵² ('-s 2000000 --pi 90 -c 100000') (Jain [et al.](#), 2018a) v3.1.3.

1.5 Base accuracy and assembly completeness

To assess base accuracy and completeness, specifically Mercury's quality values (QV) and 21-mer genome completeness (%), I used Mercury (Rhie [et al.](#), 2020) v1.3. Mercury was run three times using different *k*-mer databases: Illumina, HiFi, and a hybrid 21-mer database combining Illumina and HiFi reads, as explained above, in the "Consensus polishing" section. To assess functional completeness and evaluate the completeness of the gene set, I used the lineage of ray-finned fishes and BUSCO ('-l actinopterygii_odb10') (Simão [et al.](#), 2015) v5.6.1. Finally, nucleotide accuracy was verified by read-to-assembly mapping, performed using minimap2 ('-ax map-hifi --secondary=no') and Winnowmap ('-W repetitive.15.txt') at MAPQ >10 for HiFi reads, while for ONT reads I used the '-ax map-ont' preset for minimap2 and the '-ax map-pb' preset in Winnowmap MAPQ >10. For Visualisations, I used IGV ('igv -g \$genome \$BAM(s) \$mercury_only_bed_wig_kmer_files').

⁵²MashMap2 is a fast and approximate algorithm for computing whole-genome homology maps. It uses minimizer-based locality-sensitive hashing to rapidly identify high-confidence regions of sequence similarity, making it suitable for genome-to-genome alignments, structural variation detection, and reference-guided scaffolding (Jain [et al.](#), 2018a).

Results – Bighead Catfish

The haplotype-resolved *de novo* assembly resulted in 27 Hi-C scaffolds, and the chromosome number was $2n = 2x = 54$ pseudochromosomes (Maneechot et al., 2016).

1. Raw Read Quality

Figure 15 summarizes raw data quality for the bighead catfish genome.

Figure 15 Sequencing summary and genome survey of bighead catfish. **(A)** Sequencing protocols and coverages. **(B)** GenomeScope *k*-mer profile showing genome size, repeat content, and 17.6% heterozygosity. **(C)** HiFi reads: high quality and 15 kbp peak length. **(D)** ONT reads: broader size range with N50 30 kbp and moderate quality.

2. Global Assembly Metrics

Sequence variation analysis⁵³ was performed with PlotSR suite (Goel and Schneeberger, 2022), revealing 1,968,666 heterozygous SNPs across both haplotypes after `minimap2 (-ax asm5)` cross-haplotype mapping, resulting in a heterozygosity rate⁵⁴ of 0.594%. Structural variant analysis identified 392,973 insertions totaling 7.67 Mb in Haplotype 2, while Haplotype 1 had 393,127 deletions spanning 7.75 Mb. Copy number variations⁵⁵ included 114 copy gains in Haplotype 2 (184 Kb) and 123 copy losses in Haplotype 1 (416 Kb). Highly divergent regions⁵⁶ were identified, spanning 57.9 Mb in Haplotype 1 and 56.0 Mb in Haplotype 2. Additionally, 47 tandem repeat clusters⁵⁷ were detected, covering 10 Kb in Haplotype 1 and 7 Kb in Haplotype 2.

Table 1 Summary statistics of the haplotype-resolved *Clarias macrocephalus* genome assembly.

Features	Haplotype 1	Haplotype 2
Overall quality (x.y.P.Q.C)	6.30.P7.53.Q48.C94.25	6.30.P7.53.Q48.C94.25
Genome size (Mb)	875 Mb	880 Mb
pseudochromosomes	27	27
Mitochondrion length (bp)	16,510 bp	N/A
NG50 of contigs (Mb)	3 Mb	3 Mb
N50 of scaffolds (Mb)	34 Mb	34 Mb
LG50/LG90 of scaffolds	11 / 24 (Hap1)	11 / 24 (Hap2)
Number of gaps	752	653
GC content (%)	39.32%	39.32%
Complete BUSCOs N (%)	93.0% (Hap1)	93.5% (Hap2)
Median QV (Mercury k21)	42.99 (Hap1)	43.33 (Hap2) 48.22 (All)
Completeness (Mercury k21)	89.11 (Hap1)	88.88 (Hap2) 95.25 (All)

⁵³Comparison of Haplotype 1 and 2 chromosomes to detect heterozygous variants such as SNPs, indels, and structural changes.

⁵⁴Proportion of sites where the two haplotypes differ, reflecting allelic diversity.

⁵⁵Duplications or deletions causing variable copy numbers of genomic regions.

⁵⁶Genomic segments showing strong sequence divergence between haplotypes or species.

⁵⁷Short motifs repeated head-to-tail, often in telomeres or centromeres.

3. Hi-C Contact Validation

3.1 Haplotype 1 – Hi-C Contact Matrix

Figure 16 Hi-C contact matrix heat maps displaying individual pseudochromosome scaffolds in Haplotype 1, sorted by length.

3.2 Haplotype 2 – Hi-C Contact Matrix

Figure 17 Hi-C contact matrix heat maps displaying individual pseudo-chromosome scaffolds in Haplotype 2, sorted by length.

3.3 Genome-Wide Hi-C Maps – Haplotype 1 and 2

(A) Hi-C map of Hi-C scaffolds - Haplotype 1

(B) Hi-C map of Hi-C scaffolds - Haplotype 2

Figure 18 Hi-C map of pseudochromosome scaffolds in bighead catfish.

4. Genome Completeness Evaluation

To assess the completeness and accuracy of the Bighead catfish genome assembly, we performed complementary analyses using k -mer spectra (Merqury) and BUSCO benchmarking (Figure 19).

Panel (A) shows the distinct k -mer spectrum, where the grey “read-only” peak represents missing or low-coverage regions, indicating that a small portion of the genome was not captured in the assembly. The red and blue peaks correspond to 1-copy and 2-copy k -mers, respectively, while the green “shared” k -mers dominate the homozygous peak—consistent with a largely complete, diploid genome. Panel (B) presents the BUSCO assessment results for the Flye collapsed assembly (used as a positive control) and the two Hifiasm haplotype-resolved assemblies. The Flye assembly shows higher duplication, whereas both Hifiasm assemblies exhibit near-complete recovery of single-copy orthologs and reduced duplication, confirming improved assembly quality. Panel (C) displays the copy-number spectrum, where a modest $3\times$ peak (green) suggests limited false duplication. Such residual duplications could be mitigated with purging tools such as PurgeDups (Guan *et al.*, 2020) or Purge Haplotigs (Roach *et al.*, 2018) before Hi-C scaffolding.

5. Scaffold Metrics

Per-scaffold analyses confirmed uniform base and structural accuracy across chromosomes. Key quality metrics included base accuracy (median QV \approx 50), gap content, and telomere orientation. Structural integrity was assessed using the Structural Assembly Quality Index (S-AQI %), base-level accuracy with Merqury ($k=21$), structural precision with CRAQ, telomere polarity with QuarTeT (+ inward, – outward, > 100 repeats), and gap statistics with Detgaps.

(A) Distant K-mer assembly spectra

Figure 19 Integrated assessment of Bighead catfish genome completeness. (A) Distinct k -mer assembly spectra showing read-only (grey), haplotype-specific (red and blue), and shared (green) k -mers. (B) BUSCO completeness comparison across assemblies showing reduced duplication and high completeness in both Hifiasm haplotypes. (C) Copy-number k -mer spectrum showing a small $3\times$ peak indicating minimal duplication.

Table 2 Summary of scaffold metrics in the haplotype-resolved genome assembly of *Clarias macrocephalus*, **Haplotype 1**.

Scaffold Name	Size	Errors	Quality Values	Gaps	Left Telomere	Right Telomere	S-AQI
Haplotype_Linkage	(Mb)	21-mer	hyb.k21.meryl	(N)	(5' AACCCCT)	(AGGGTT 3')	(%)
fClaMac_1_LG_01	48,4	3242	54.8396	23	Left 507 (-)	-	93.24
fClaMac_1_LG_02	46,18	6400	51.574	24	Left 607 (+)	Right 1016 (-)	73.94
fClaMac_1_LG_03	40,54	6784	50.6951	20	-	Right 215 (-)	91.18
fClaMac_1_LG_04	37,64	4160	52.7678	23	Left 147 (+)	Right 122 (-)	100.00
fClaMac_1_LG_05	37,19	9007	49.2436	23	Left 579 (+)	Right 190 (-)	93.23
fClaMac_1_LG_06	37,01	5548	51.4013	25	-	-	84.09
fClaMac_1_LG_07	34,64	7089	49.8928	25	Left 214 (+)	-	93.24
fClaMac_1_LG_08	47,03	12668	48.7208	32	Left 170 (+)	Right 190 (-)	89.37
fClaMac_1_LG_09	28,28	7205	49.2196	13	Left 153 (+)	Right 1630 (-)	81.31
fClaMac_1_LG_10	29,87	12042	47.0424	24	Left 282 (+)	-	95.23
fClaMac_1_LG_11	25,51	6087	49.3463	19	Left 1008 (+)	-	80.92
fClaMac_1_LG_12	28,04	8367	48.2834	21	Left 124 (+)	-	95.73
fClaMac_1_LG_13	24,08	3715	51.2825	18	Left 377 (+)	-	86.62
fClaMac_1_LG_14	21,22	4707	49.7286	13	-	Right 136 (-)	94.05
fClaMac_1_LG_15	25,46	3974	51.1515	20	Left 127 (+)	Right 115 (-)	95.00
fClaMac_1_LG_16	24,8	4054	50.9451	15	-	Right 109 (-)	73.65
fClaMac_1_LG_17	22,98	67523	38.5013	15	Left 120 (+)	-	77.54
fClaMac_1_LG_18	24,8	2060	53.9205	13	-	-	90.26
fClaMac_1_LG_19	31,01	3329	52.8263	22	-	Right 363 (-)	92.45
fClaMac_1_LG_20	30,49	4074	51.8251	15	-	Right 406 (-)	83.79
fClaMac_1_LG_21	28,95	4609	51.2	28	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_1_LG_22	33,48	2784	54.0062	23	-	Right 904 (-)	92.37
fClaMac_1_LG_23	31,45	8435	48.8646	16	-	Right 790 (-)	86.84
fClaMac_1_LG_24	28,07	4984	50.6636	12	Left 423 (+)	-	88.33
fClaMac_1_LG_25	38,33	6711	50.6434	24	-	-	96.55
fClaMac_1_LG_26	40,06	4967	52.1555	21	Left 556 (+)	Right 604 (-)	87.85
fClaMac_1_LG_27	29,17	2146	54.5417	13	-	-	74.96

Table 3 Summary of scaffold metrics in the haplotype-resolved genome assembly of *Clarias macrocephalus*, **Haplotype 2**.

Scaffold Name	Size	Errors	Quality Values	Gaps	Left Telomere	Right Telomere	S-AQI
Haplotype_Linkage	(Mb)	21-mer	hyb.k21.meryl	(N)	(5') AACCCCT)	(AGGGTT 3')	(%)
fClaMac_2_LG_01	51,51	2649	55.5298	17	-	-	89.28
fClaMac_2_LG_02	44,94	6893	51.161	25	Left 255 (+)	-	71.62
fClaMac_2_LG_03	39,44	8894	49.5912	16	-	-	83.57
fClaMac_2_LG_04	38,01	6912	50.5588	18	Left 293 (+)	Right 526 (-)	88.17
fClaMac_2_LG_05	38,16	3424	53.4601	23	-	Right 125 (-)	78.26
fClaMac_2_LG_06	38,66	2675	54.3325	17	-	-	80.86
fClaMac_2_LG_07	33,93	5651	50.8217	17	Left 169 (+)	-	89.91
fClaMac_2_LG_08	47,19	10458	49.5856	29	Left 174 (+)	Right 190 (-)	89.44
fClaMac_2_LG_09	28,8	10239	47.5736	14	Left 641 (+)	-	91.91
fClaMac_2_LG_10	29,07	5001	50.8593	14	Left 268 (+)	-	95.24
fClaMac_2_LG_11	25,76	6627	48.9338	21	-	-	89.75
fClaMac_2_LG_12	30,93	6915	48.7951	19	-	-	82.58
fClaMac_2_LG_13	23,66	3213	51.9117	15	-	Right 100 (+)	86.65
fClaMac_2_LG_14	21,06	3487	50.9324	7	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_15	24,93	7673	48.2988	17	Left 134 (+)	Right 137 (-)	85.58
fClaMac_2_LG_16	24,83	3011	52.2777	10	-	-	81.74
fClaMac_2_LG_17	22,34	2012	53.6414	15	Left 175 (+)	-	85.99
fClaMac_2_LG_18	24,44	1986	54.0521	11	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_19	30,86	3566	52.521	16	-	Right 362 (-)	90.62
fClaMac_2_LG_20	34,51	2384	53.5357	13	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_21	27,99	2550	53.5741	13	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_22	33,35	4588	51.8225	16	Left 128 (+)	Right 908 (-)	88.64
fClaMac_2_LG_23	31,45	9701	48.2459	6	Left 214 (+)	Right 793 (-)	82.68
fClaMac_2_LG_24	27,39	2840	53.0349	6	Left 114 (+)	-	93.87
fClaMac_2_LG_25	37,88	7891	49.9914	15	-	-	87.01
fClaMac_2_LG_26	40,17	11271	48.6822	13	-	Right 607 (-)	88.08
fClaMac_2_LG_27	29,56	1236	56.9751	12	Left 155 (+)	-	90.78
MT_from_NC_046749	0,02	-	-	-	-	-	-

6. TE Metrics

6.1 Dating of TE Replicative Bursts

To estimate the expansion history of major transposable element (TE) superfamilies in *Clarias macrocephalus*, I calculated the nucleotide divergence of each TE copy relative to its consensus sequence and converted this divergence into approximate insertion ages using a neutral mutation rate⁵⁸ ($\mu = 6 \times 10^{-9}$ per site per generation) previously determined in electric catfish (Liu *et al.*, 2023b). Assuming a one-year generation time, the estimated expansion peaks indicate that LTR/Gypsy and TIR/Mutator families expanded around 30–33 Mya, LTR/Copia and TIR/hAT around 28–30 Mya, and TIR/CACTA, PIF/Harbinger, and Tc1/Mariner families between 16 and 25 Mya. These results (Figure 20) reveal multiple waves of TE proliferation, likely reflecting episodes of genome instability or evolutionary transition in the species' history.

Figure 20 TE divergence profiles in bighead catfish genome.

⁵⁸The neutral mutation rate is the rate at which mutations accumulate in non-functional genomic regions, providing a baseline for molecular-clock dating.

6.2 Genome composition in TE

Transposable element (TE) annotation indicated that 35.25% of the bighead catfish genome consisted of repetitive sequences. Among these, TIR DNA transposons comprised 19.12%, Helitrons 4.47%, LTR retrotransposons 8.30%, LINE elements 0.46%, and the remaining 2.82% consisted of uncharacterized repeats.

Table 4 Transposable element content in Bighead catfish Haplotype 1.

Class	Superfamily	Haplotype 1	Haplotype 2
	Features	# of elements	
LINE	<i>I</i>	128	
	<i>L1</i>	547	
	<i>L2</i>	1,129	
	<i>Rex</i>	556	
	LINE/Unknown	7,412	
LTR	<i>Bel_Pao</i>	151	
	<i>Copia</i>	53	
	<i>Gypsy</i>	68,215	
	LTR/Unknown	13,466	
TIR	<i>CACTA</i>	357,388	
	<i>Mutator</i>	172,578	
	<i>PIF_Harbinger</i>	36,538	
	<i>Tc1_Mariner</i>	41,500	
	<i>hAT</i>	80,189	
	<i>PiggyBac</i>	758	
	<i>Polinton</i>	281	
NonLTR	<i>DIRS_YR</i>	678	
	<i>Penelope</i>	417	
NonTIR	<i>Helitron</i>	166,251	
Other	Repeat Fragment	78,900	
	Total Interspersed	1,148,329	

LINEs (Long Interspersed Nuclear Elements) are non-LTR retrotransposons that transpose via a copy-and-paste mechanism using reverse transcriptase; although less abundant in fish genomes than in mammals, they contribute to structural variation. LTR retrotransposons replicate through an RNA intermediate using reverse transcription and are flanked by long terminal repeats, playing key roles in genome expansion and gene regulation. TIR DNA transposons (Terminal Inverted Repeat transposons) are cut-and-paste elements flanked by inverted repeats recognized by a transposase enzyme, contributing to genome rearrangement and regulatory diversification. Non-LTR retrotransposons such as DIRS and Penelope elements add further diversity to the repetitive landscape through distinct mobilization mechanisms. Helitrons, belonging to the NonTIR class, are rolling-circle DNA transposons that lack terminal inverted repeats and transpose through a mechanism similar to rolling-circle replication, often capturing and mobilizing gene fragments that promote genomic innovation. Together, these TE classes reflect a dynamic evolutionary history for *C. macrocephalus*, consistent with high DNA transposon activity typical of teleost genomes.

7. Macrosynteny Analysis

To examine orthologous relationships and identify syntenic regions between catfish and related teleost species, I obtained proteomes (.pep.fa files) from Ensembl v2024 (Harrison et al., 2023), ensuring the latest assembly versions for consistency. Species are *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (USDA_OmykA_1.1), *Oryzias latipes* (ASM223467v1), *Lates calcarifer* (ASB_HGAPassembly_v1), *Cyprinus carpio* (Cypcar_WagV4.0), *Danio rerio* (GRCz11), *Oreochromis niloticus* (O_niloticus_UMD_NMBU), and *Lepisosteus oculatus* (LepOcu1). Orthologous gene clusters (Orthogroups) were first identified with OrthoFinder ('orthofinder -f /proteomes -M msa -a 126 -t 126') (Emms and Kelly, 2019) v.2.5.5. Subsequently, I utilized xrhbexpress (<https://github.com/SamiLhl/rbhXpress>) and macrosyntR (El Hilali and Copley, 2023) v0.2.19 to analyze the resulting orthogroups and visualize their syntenic relationships across species. This combined approach allowed for an in-depth view of conserved and divergent genomic regions within the catfish lineage and related teleosts (Figure 21).

(A) Whole-genome four-way synteny analysis

Figure 21 Synteny analysis for various catfish samples. **(A)** Whole-genome 4-way synteny analysis from 1413 shared single-copy orthogroups across *Clarias gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2), *Clarias macrocephalus*, *Danio rerio* (GRCz11) *Danio rerio* and *Oreochromis niloticus* (O_niloticus_UMD_NMBU), reveals conserved chromosome structures and rearrangements. **(B)** Simple phylogeny and geological timescales (TimeTree5, <https://timetree.org/>).

Results – F1 Hybrid Catfish

The haplotype-resolved *de novo* assembly of the F1 hybrid catfish (*C. macrocephalus* × *C. gariepinus*) yielded a total of 55 Hi-C scaffolds, representing 27 + 28 chromosomes from the parental species (Lewin [et al.](#), 2019; Manechot [et al.](#), 2016).

1. Raw Read Quality

Figure 22 summarizes the sequencing data quality and genome survey statistics.

Figure 22 Sequencing summary and genome survey of the F1 hybrid catfish (*C. macrocephalus* × *C. gariepinus*). **(A)** GenomeScope2.0 *k*-mer profile (*k*=21) estimating genome size (903 Mb), heterozygosity (10.1%), and sequencing error rate (0.28%). **(B)** Sequencing coverage by data type: HiFi (30×), ONT (36×), Hi-C (37×), and Illumina (55×). **(C)** HiFi reads show high quality with 15 kbp modal length. **(D)** ONT reads display broader length distribution (N50 ≈ 30 kbp).

1.1 Illumina paired-end short-reads

Standard Illumina paired-end short-reads sequencing [Bentley et al. \(2008\)](#) was performed on the Illumina NextSeq2000 platform (by NovoGene), resulting in more than 50 Gb of raw read data (read-length=151 nucleotides), which is equivalent to a genome coverage of 36X. Raw reads had an average quality of Q25, and 92% of the dataset had a median quality of Q30.

1.2 Proximity-ligation (Hi-C) paired-end short-reads

Proximity-ligation (Hi-C) data was obtained by following a standard *in situ* Hi-C protocol from 2009 [Dudchenko et al. \(2017\)](#). Briefly, a nuclear ligation was performed by cross-linking chromosomes, then a restriction digestion was carried out with DpnII endonuclease. The chromatin conformation capture library was prepared using Phase Genomics (<https://info.phasegenomics.com/protocols>), and the genomic DNA was sequenced on the Illumina NextSeq2000 platform, resulting in paired-end short-reads (151 nucleotides in length) for 37.19 Gb of raw data (approximately 100M pairs of reads per billion bases in genome length) corresponding to a genome coverage of 39.77X. 97.18% of the dataset had a quality score of Q30 or higher (Supplementary Table 3). For Haplotype 1, 123.96M read pairs were sequenced, yielding 74.77M unique Hi-C contacts, with 59.40M valid contacts (22.71M inter-chromosomal, 36.69M intra-chromosomal), including 17.47M short-range (<20Kb) and 19.72M long-range (>20Kb) contacts. Haplotype 2 showed similar metrics.

1.3 PacBio HiFi long-reads

PacBio's HiFi long-read sequencing was performed using a SMRT cell on the Sequel II system, resulting in 10.62 Gb of raw data corresponding to a genome coverage of approximately 12.9X or 6-7X per haplotype. The read length N50 value was 10,379 bases, the raw reads' mean quality score was Q28.7, and the median quality score was Q36. Over 72% were above Q30, and 86% above Q25. There were 191,790

reads with a cumulative length of 5,066,253,114 bases (5 Gb) in the high-quality reads subset ($> Q10$).

1.4 Oxford nanopore technologies (ONT) 1D-long noisy reads

ONT long noisy reads were prepared from 1D-fragmented and size-selected pooled libraries of end-polished, nick-repaired, and A-tailed DNA fragments, produced by ligating sequencing adapters onto double-stranded DNA fragments purified with AMPure XP beads. DNA quality was assessed with QuBit before sequencing on the Nanopore MiniION system (NovoGene). The standard ONT libraries comprised 32.62 Gb of raw read data, corresponding to a genome coverage of 36X, or 18X per haplotype. The read N50 value was 4 kb. We estimate an ONT data median read quality of Q11, with 97.0% of reads having quality $> Q7$ (4,023,582 reads), corresponding to 20% base-errors. Unfortunately the quality of the data was extremely low resulting in only $< 4X$ of genome coverage of reads usable from 36X sequenced.

2. Global Assembly Metrics

Our F1 hybrid catfish genome released into GenBank consists of 55 scaffolds (all exceeding 10,000 bp), totaling 1,858,695,542 bp, one mtDNA and 0 unplaced sequences. Notably, every contig in scaffolds exceeds 1,000,000 bp, with the longest spanning 51,692,840 bp and the second longest being 51,114,572 bp which correspond to a Telomere-to-Telomere (T2T) chromosome with 0 gaps. Our assembly reached an N50 of 33,844,116 bp which is an indicator of high contiguity. Read-to-contig HiFi minimap2 alignment performed in the context of Inspector confirms a 99.96% mapping rate, a 0.52% split-read rate, and an average mapped depth of 10.65 \times , which remains consistent for contigs > 1 Mbp. Structural validation identified 22 structural errors (12 expansions, 7 collapses, 2 to 5 haplotype switches, and 1 inversion), while small-scale errors averaged 4.79 per Mbp (8,897 total), comprising 6,226 base substitutions, 1,189 expansions, and 1,482 collapses. Further quality control was performed with Merqury ($k=21$) to evaluate k -mer-based metrics (Figure 25, Table 5 and Table 6). Consensus Quality

Values (QVs) for the hybrid genome and each sub-genome were 50.1, 48.3, and 49.5, respectively, with k -mer completeness scores of 96.7%, 95.8%, and 97.4% for hybrid (2 haps, combined), bighead, and North African catfish sub-genomes. Merqury's spectrum analysis confirmed the high quality and completeness of the haplotype-resolved assembly with minimal assembly errors. Overall, the polished assembly achieved a QV of 50.28 (pileup-based, Inspector v1.3), indicating a robust base-level accuracy and structural integrity suitable for various types of downstream analyses.

3. Comparative synteny with previous *C. macrocephalus* and *C. gariepinus*

Comparative synteny analyses revealed extensive genomic conservation between the hybrid catfish genome and its parental species (Appendix Figure 31; Appendix Figure 32). In the North African catfish (*C. gariepinus*) comparison, macrosynteny across 28 pseudo-chromosomes indicated strong structural collinearity with the hybrid genome, interrupted only by localized inversions, translocations, and small duplicated regions. The overall sequence variation landscape was dominated by highly divergent regions and SNPs, while structural variants represented a minor fraction of total differences. Similarly, in the Bighead catfish (*C. macrocephalus*) comparison, 27 pseudo-chromosomes showed high collinearity and preserved chromosomal organization, confirming the structural stability of both parental lineages. Variation analyses identified modest insertions, deletions, and inversion tracts, consistent with evolutionary divergence preceding hybridization. Together, these results indicate that both parental genomes contributed largely conserved chromosomal architectures to the hybrid lineage, supporting a high-quality, structurally stable hybrid genome assembly.

3.1 Expected Genome Sizes, k -mer Profiles and Hybrid Genome Assessment

(Appendix Figure 30) presents GenomeScope2.0 k -mer profiles to evaluate genome size, heterozygosity, and repeat content for the F1 hybrid genome and its parental species. Separate k -mer distributions are shown for individual parental lineages from distinct bloodlines to assess intra-species variation.

- **Parental individuals (same species, different bloodlines):** The *C. macrocephalus* individual exhibits low heterozygosity (~0.056%), while *C. gariepinus* shows moderate heterozygosity (~1.56%), consistent with expected intraspecific levels. Broader peaks at $k=21$ likely reflect lower Illumina coverage (<20×), but species-level divergence remains evident.
- **F1 hybrid genome:** At $k=21$, the estimated genome size is approximately 1.8 Gb, aligning with the combined haploid contributions of both species. The apparent heterozygosity rate of 10% reflects typical divergence in inter-specific F1 hybrids with distinct sub-genomes. This divergence results in a bimodal distribution due to haplotype differences. At $k=31$, heterozygosity estimates in the F1 hybrid decrease as k -mer size increases, reflecting partial subgenome separation and reducing false overlaps.

4. Hi-C Contact Validation

Separate Hi-C contact matrices were generated for each chromosome-scale scaffold in the F1 hybrid genome to confirm subgenome identity and structural integrity. As shown in Figures 23 and 24, the two sub-genomes display distinct, internally consistent chromosomal contact patterns, supporting successful haplotype separation and chromosome-scale phasing.

- **African catfish subgenome (28 chromosomes):** The majority of scaffolds show strong diagonal contact patterns without major off-diagonal disruptions, indicating high contiguity and few mis-joins. A few chromosomes exhibit minor local noise or contact gaps, which were further curated using Juicebox manual correction and IGV inspection.
- **Bighead catfish subgenome (27 chromosomes):** Hi-C interaction maps demonstrate similar quality, with well-defined diagonals consistent with chromosome-length assemblies. Chromosomes such as Chr07 and Chr23 displayed additional

off-diagonal signals that were manually split or trimmed to eliminate structural noise.

Together, these Hi-C maps validate the scaffolded genome structure of each parental haplotype in the F1 hybrid assembly. Their visual clarity and signal symmetry confirm that subgenome resolution was successful and that the assembly faithfully represents the diploid karyotype ($2n = 55$) of the hybrid genome.

4.1 Haplotype – North African catfish subgenome

This panel shows the intra-chromosomal Hi-C contact maps of the *Clarias gariepinus* haplotype in the F1 hybrid.

Figure 23 Hi-C interaction maps for the 28 pseudochromosomes of the North African catfish subgenome.

4.2 Haplotype – Bighead catfish subgenome

This figure displays the Hi-C contact maps for the *Clarias macrocephalus* haplotype in the same F1 hybrid.

Figure 24 Hi-C interaction maps for the 27 pseudochromosomes of the bighead catfish subgenome.

5. Genome Completeness Evaluation

To further validate gene content and completeness, BUSCO analysis (Figure 25) was performed, yielding high completeness scores. For the North African catfish sub-genome, 97.1% of core genes were complete [95.7% single-copy, 1.4% duplicated], with 2.2% missing. The bighead catfish sub-genome showed similar completeness, with 96.6% of core genes [95.3% single-copy, 1.3% duplicated] and 2.7% missing. This analysis underscores the high integrity and completeness of gene content within the assembly.

Notably, the F1 genome exceeded 97% BUSCO completeness (Fig. 25B) and achieved a median QV of 55 (Mercury Figs. 25D, 25E), with no multiplicity peaks over 2 \times —indicating near-reference-grade assemblies. Together with k -mer analysis and BUSCO metrics, these profiles confirm the F1 hybrid assembly's completeness, chromosome number consistency (27 + 28), and dual subgenome contribution, while BUSCO-derived gene synteny in *Clarias* confirms the F1 hybrid nature of the genome two subspecies (Fig. 25F). One mitochondrial sequence, confirmed through IGV polymorphism analysis, belongs to *C. macrocephalus*. Other results were a final assembly k -mer completeness estimated at 99.4% ($k=21$, Mercury) to 99.38% ($k=31$, Mercury),

Figure 25 Overview of F1 Hybrid Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* × *Clarias macrocephalus*) genome assembly validation. Hi-C phasing confirms 55 pseudochromosomes, with BUSCO scores indicating 97% gene completeness. Synteny analysis and *k*-mer distributions support the F1 hybrid nature, demonstrating chromosome separation into sub-genomes and their evolutionary affiliations.

6. Scaffold Metrics

6.1 Assembly Statistics and Quality Assessment

Assembly metrics are summarized in Table 5 and Table 6, including scaffold count, length in Mb, QV, error rates, and scaffold length in bases, with a gradient indicating QV quality: red for $QV < 50$, yellow for QV between 50-60, and green for $QV > 60$. The leftmost column displays the count of error seqmers (k -mers present in the assembly but absent in reads), indicating potential assembly errors. Alongside are given the relative telomeres orientation ($5'$ + inward \rightarrow / \leftarrow inward - $3'$), and gaps count in chromosomes.

Structural validation, performed using 3D-DNA and JBAT, confirmed scaffold accuracy, with additional polishing steps through NextPolish2, TGS GapCloser, Pilon, and automated consensus polishing using ONT 1D reads, Racon, Merfin, and BCFtools, resulting in a final quality score of QV50, a 99.999% base precision, 99% mapping rate, and 99.4% k -mer completeness. Despite the presence of complex repeats, the assembly achieved CRAQ structural accuracy (S-AQI) above 97%, indicating reference-grade quality (Li et al., 2023).

6.2 Comparative Analysis of Subgenomes

North African catfish scaffolds exhibit consistently higher QVs (up to ~65.79) than bighead catfish scaffolds (ranging ~50–54), indicating fewer sequence errors and higher assembly quality overall. Several chromosomes exhibit Telomere-to-Telomere (T2T) continuity, validating successful resolution of full-length chromosomes. North African catfish scaffolds contain fewer unclosed gaps than bighead catfish, reflecting superior completeness and assembly contiguity. Note that this may result from local genome complexity or differences in transposable element content and diversity, aside from variations in raw sequencing data quality.

Table 5 North African subgenome scaffold metrics with Quality Values from Merquy ($k=21$ and $k=31$), telomere orientation, and gap counts.

Scaffold_name	Length	QV_k21	Errors_k21	QV_k31	Errors_k31	Left_telomere	Gaps	Right_telomere
Sub-Genome_Chromosome	Mb.	21-mer	21-mer	31-mer	31-mer	(5' AACCT)	(N)	(AGGGTT 3')
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_01	51,1	64.5442	377	59.4881	1783	119 (+)	T2T	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_02	51,7	56.0219	2713	56.0911	3942	174 (+)	1	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_03	47,6	59.3028	1174	54.5941	5125	1701 (+)	3	1603 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_04	44,3	49.4714	10490	56.9825	2716	185 (+)	8	160 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_05	41,5	62.5139	488	61.5864	892	1472 (+)	T2T	1883 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_06	41,3	54.5824	3021	56.2081	3068	278 (+)	1	1447 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_07	42,6	58.0864	1389	54.3111	4889	384 (+)	3	382 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_08	40,2	54.3182	3124	59.8602	1287	0	T2T	130 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_09	37,3	55.9044	2013	53.8378	4784	1449 (+)	1	315 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_10	34,9	67.6478	126	60.3736	993	0	2	127 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_11	33,5	51.4996	4986	58.2486	1555	1614 (+)	T2T	1997 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_12	35,3	54.4649	2653	58.1993	1657	0	6	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_13	33,6	66.4695	159	63.3235	483	1525 (+)	2	1557 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_14	32,4	47.2905	12717	61.6029	690	105 (+)	T2T	226 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_15	35	64.2407	275	58.2795	1602	328 (+)	2	118 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_16	33,8	60.5363	627	57.9679	1675	1602 (+)	4	137 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_17	30,3	55.2666	1892	56.604	2052	335 (-)	T2T	276 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_18	30,5	56.641	1382	57.9088	1522	1411 (+)	3	2289 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_19	30,7	64.5469	226	58.6026	1311	784 (+)	2	178 (+)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_20	27,1	57.0276	1128	60.0252	835	171 (+)	2	406 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_21	30,6	60.6832	549	60.1377	919	1936 (+)	2	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_22	30	62.328	369	60.2163	886	0	2	129 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_23	26,2	52.9697	2773	58.0814	1260	279 (+)	1	1739 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_24	25,9	60.3587	501	60.6659	689	185 (+)	2	114 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_25	25,6	58.5637	748	59.0404	989	232 (+)	T2T	129 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_26	26,3	56.7889	1163	57.358	1506	1343 (+)	3	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_27	24	68.2243	76	59.5233	832	0	T2T	264 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_28	20,3	59.8335	443	56.9713	1261	0	2	0

Table 6 Bighead subgenome scaffold metrics with Quality Values from Merqury ($k=21$ and $k=31$), telomere orientation, and gap counts.

Scaffold_name	Length	QV_k21	Errors_k21	QV_k31	Errors_k31	Left_telomere	Gaps	Right_telomere
Sub-Genome_Chromosome	Mb.	21-mer	21-mer	31-mer	31-mer	(5' AACCT)	(N)	(AGGGTT 3')
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_01	50,1	55.7992	2767	50.7048	13207	998 (+)	14	740 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_02	44,3	51.8276	6102	54.4421	4934	815 (+)	5	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_03	40,4	44.33	31251	55.4715	3531	327 (+)	12	279 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_04	38,4	52.1302	4933	52.1322	7281	222 (+)	13	819 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_05	38,1	47.0334	15835	53.7219	4994	321 (+)	14	301 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_06	37,4	52.5469	4370	50.6785	9921	282 (+)	14	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_07	33,8	50.998	5644	48.4795	14888	924 (+)	15	629 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_08	45,6	56.2767	2252	51.0889	10984	161 (+)	11	1237 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_09	30	48.1331	9677	48.5674	12936	184 (+)	13	751 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_10	29,8	54.8059	2065	49.5164	10314	316 (+)	12	664 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_11	25	51.0866	4085	53.4888	3469	0	21	267 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_12	31,6	48.5768	9241	47.4853	17546	559 (+)	13	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_13	24,9	44.8933	16909	48.6904	10418	740 (+)	8	220 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_14	23,3	44.5272	17249	51.8503	4715	0	8	190 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_15	27,6	39.2488	68816	52.3266	4848	200 (+)	12	107 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_16	25,2	51.936	3389	53.2655	3686	656 (+)	9	818 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_17	24	40.0722	49568	46.7745	15616	326 (+)	15	222 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_18	25,2	52.6726	2856	52.3131	4582	632 (+)	11	973 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_19	31,1	53.8536	2692	52.9809	4841	674 (+)	8	751 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_20	32,7	51.6697	4681	51.0227	7929	410 (+)	18	422 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_21	29,2	43.0312	30479	51.9822	5662	805 (+)	16	253 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_22	34,9	51.0828	5705	50.9355	8715	568 (+)	13	121 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_23	31,7	42.7592	35295	48.8582	12797	931 (+)	8	1022 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_24	29,6	50.1103	6080	52.8055	4829	851 (+)	10	159 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_25	40,3	52.391	4875	52.1653	7582	0	9	798 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_26	40,1	53.1914	4035	51.6319	8529	1038 (+)	11	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_27	30,5	48.7036	8641	48.5145	13324	1858 (+)	10	219 (-)

6.3 Structural Accuracy Assessment

Table 7 and Table 8 present structural accuracy metrics from CRAQ for both sub-genomes, including Structural Accuracy Index (S-AQI), Regional Accuracy (R-AQI), and heterozygous loci for structural and regional metrics (Avg.CSH/Avg.CRH). Note that CRH and CSH values are expected to be close to 0 due to the high genomic diversity between the two parental species (divergence > 10%, mash-based ([Ondov et al., 2019](#)), not shown here).

North African catfish scaffolds displayed near-perfect S-AQI and R-AQI values, both ranging approximately from 97% to 100%, indicating minimal misassemblies at both large-scale and regional-scale levels. In contrast, bighead catfish scaffolds exhibited slightly lower accuracy, with S-AQI values around 90–97% and R-AQI between 90–96%. This reduction in quality may be attributed to factors such as lower species heterozygosity, increased local assembly complexity due to transposable element content, or potential sequencing quality issues, possibly arising from degraded genomic DNA used in ONT sequencing.

Table 7 North African subgenome structural accuracy metrics from CRAQ: S-AQI, R-AQI, and heterozygous regions (Avg.CSH/Avg.CRH).

Scaffold_name	Mapping.rate	Avg.CRH	Avg.CRE	Avg.CSE	Regional-AQI	Avg.CSH	Structural-AQI
Sub-Genome_Chromosome	ONT/PE (%)	Count	Count	Count	Accuracy (%)	Count	Accuracy (%)
Genome (55 Chromosomes)	>97%	0.046	0.270	0.021	97.33	0.001	97.92
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_01	0.992	0.020	0.078	0.000	99.22	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_02	0.981	0.000	0.098	0.000	99.02	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_03	0.955	0.033	0.154	0.000	98.47	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_04	0.980	0.046	0.207	0.046	97.95	0.000	95.50
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_05	0.986	0.048	0.097	0.000	99.04	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_06	0.998	0.024	0.085	0.000	99.15	0.024	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_07	0.978	0.000	0.120	0.000	98.81	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_08	0.992	0.025	0.100	0.000	99.00	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_09	0.992	0.076	0.083	0.027	99.17	0.000	97.34
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_10	0.998	0.066	0.172	0.000	98.29	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_11	0.905	0.030	0.188	0.000	98.13	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_12	0.873	0.086	0.230	0.000	97.72	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_13	0.917	0.075	0.119	0.000	98.81	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_14	0.990	0.031	0.062	0.062	99.38	0.000	93.96
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_15	0.922	0.076	0.152	0.000	98.49	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_16	0.952	0.000	0.248	0.000	97.55	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_17	0.997	0.033	0.083	0.000	99.18	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_18	0.954	0.175	0.315	0.000	96.90	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_19	0.998	0.000	0.294	0.033	97.10	0.000	96.79
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_20	0.995	0.056	0.148	0.000	98.53	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_21	0.986	0.033	0.131	0.098	98.70	0.000	90.65
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_22	0.992	0.067	0.134	0.034	98.67	0.000	96.70
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_23	0.998	0.058	0.186	0.038	98.16	0.000	96.23
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_24	0.999	0.077	0.232	0.000	97.71	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_25	0.989	0.039	0.118	0.000	98.83	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_26	0.994	0.057	0.324	0.000	96.81	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_27	0.980	0.042	0.166	0.000	98.35	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_28	0.995	0.000	0.297	0.000	97.07	0.000	100.00

Table 8 Bighead subgenome structural accuracy metrics from CRAQ: S-AQI, R-AQI, and heterozygous regions (Avg.CSH/Avg.CRH).

Scaffold_name	Mapping.rate	Avg.CRH	Avg.CRE	Avg.CSE	Regional-AQI	Avg.CSH	Structural-AQI
Sub-Genome_Chromosome	ONT/PE (%)	Count	Count	Count	Accuracy (%)	Count	Accuracy (%)
Genome (55 Chromosomes)	>97%	0.046	0.270	0.021	97.33	0.001	97.92
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_01	0.981	0.000	0.329	0.000	96.76	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_02	0.992	0.046	0.148	0.023	98.53	0.000	97.75
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_03	0.980	0.050	0.276	0.000	97.28	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_04	0.990	0.000	0.370	0.026	96.36	0.000	97.40
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_05	0.972	0.053	0.360	0.160	96.46	0.000	85.22
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_06	0.934	0.000	0.497	0.027	95.15	0.000	97.33
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_07	0.990	0.030	0.403	0.030	96.05	0.000	97.06
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_08	0.987	0.000	0.429	0.044	95.80	0.000	95.66
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_09	0.986	0.051	0.422	0.067	95.87	0.000	93.47
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_10	0.982	0.034	0.460	0.034	95.50	0.000	96.65
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_11	0.961	0.042	0.382	0.042	96.26	0.000	95.92
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_12	0.946	0.194	0.606	0.069	94.12	0.000	93.38
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_13	0.989	0.041	0.509	0.081	95.04	0.000	92.19
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_14	0.982	0.080	0.544	0.000	94.71	0.044	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_15	0.922	0.136	0.506	0.039	95.07	0.000	96.19
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_16	0.993	0.040	0.240	0.000	97.63	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_17	0.985	0.042	0.793	0.042	92.38	0.000	95.87
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_18	0.977	0.000	0.474	0.000	95.37	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_19	0.992	0.000	0.341	0.000	96.65	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_20	0.971	0.000	0.236	0.062	97.66	0.000	93.96
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_21	0.977	0.064	0.591	0.000	94.26	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_22	0.935	0.102	0.406	0.044	96.02	0.000	95.74
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_23	0.990	0.000	0.303	0.032	97.02	0.000	96.87
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_24	0.992	0.303	0.608	0.000	94.10	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_25	0.990	0.062	0.350	0.025	96.56	0.000	97.53
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_26	0.991	0.050	0.378	0.025	96.29	0.000	97.51
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_27	0.979	0.033	0.447	0.000	95.63	0.000	100.00

GENOME ASSEMBLY, REVERSE VACCINOLOGY, AND QUALITY BY DESIGN — *Streptococcus iniae*

Introduction

1. *Streptococcus iniae* as a Major Aquaculture Pathogen

Streptococcus iniae, first identified in an Amazon River dolphin (*Inia geoffrensis*) in the 1970s (Pier and Madin, 1976), has emerged as a major bacterial pathogen in global aquaculture. The pathogen causes annual losses exceeding USD 100 million worldwide (Shoemaker et al., 2001), with mortality rates of 30–80% during outbreaks (Chen et al., 2012) and cumulative mortality up to 70% after three months in some species (Mmanda et al., 2014). Detected across all continents (Baiano and Barnes, 2009; Mishra et al., 2018), *S. iniae* affects over 27 fish species (Agnew and Barnes, 2007), particularly in intensive aquaculture systems where high stocking densities and environmental stressors facilitate rapid disease transmission (Chen et al., 2012). Economically important species including Asian seabass (*Lates calcarifer*), tilapia (*Oreochromis* spp.), and catfish (*Siluriformes* spp.) are particularly susceptible (Azmai and Saad, 2011; Nawawi et al., 2008). While rare, zoonotic transmission to humans handling infected fish has been documented (Facklam et al., 2005).

Figure 26 Phase contrast micrograph of *S. iniae* strain QMA0076, showing characteristic spherical morphology. Credit: Baiano et al. (2008).

2. Taxonomic Classification and Molecular Characteristics

S. iniae belongs to the phylum Bacillota (formerly Firmicutes), comprising Gram-positive bacteria with thick peptidoglycan cell walls. Within the genus *Streptococcus*, *S. iniae* shares molecular mechanisms with human pathogens *S. pyogenes* and *S. pneumoniae*, particularly the sortase A pathway for cell wall protein anchoring.

Taxonomic hierarchy:

Domain: Bacteria

Phylum: Bacillota

Class: Bacilli

Order: Lactobacillales

Family: Streptococcaceae

Genus: *Streptococcus*

Species: *S. iniae*

Key virulence factors identified include M-like protein (SimA), hyaluronidase (Hyl), enolase (eno), and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH). Notably, GAPDH localizes to the outer membrane despite its primary glycolytic function, enhancing host cell adherence and immune evasion. Sortase A (SrtA) anchors these surface proteins to the cell wall through a conserved mechanism shared with other pathogenic streptococci. Despite these molecular insights, knowledge gaps remain regarding genomic variability, horizontal gene transfer, and antimicrobial resistance mechanisms.

3. Current Disease Management Challenges

Disease control in aquaculture relies primarily on broad-spectrum antibiotics (Schar [et al.](#), 2020, 2021), with vaccines serving as complementary prophylactic measures. However, vaccine adoption remains limited, particularly for low-value fresh-

water species. In Thailand, no commercial vaccines exist for *S. iniae* in barramundi (Kayansamruaj et al., 2020). The economic barrier is substantial: vaccines cost approximately 100× more than antibiotics (Hoelzer et al., 2018; Pham et al., 2015), hindering adoption despite their potential to reduce antibiotic dependence and environmental impact.

Existing whole-cell or polysaccharide-based vaccines provide only short-term protection (4–6 months) before losing efficacy due to antigenic variation (Eldar et al., 1997; Eynogor et al., 2008; Tanpichai et al., 2023). Capsular polysaccharides, traditionally considered key protective antigens, prove unstable targets as *S. iniae* rapidly alters surface structures under immune pressure. Moreover, genes responsible for capsule production belong to the accessory pangenome and are inconsistently present across strains (Millard et al., 2012), limiting broad protection.

Traditional diagnostic methods (bacterial culture, ELISA, histopathology) lack specificity, while molecular approaches (PCR, MLST) can differentiate *S. iniae* from other streptococci (Glazunova et al., 2009) but require whole-genome sequencing for accurate genotyping.

4. Study Objectives

Developing effective vaccines for *S. iniae* requires addressing both biological and manufacturing challenges. Candidate antigens must be conserved across strains, immunogenic, and compatible with scalable production processes—particularly crucial for low- to medium-value aquaculture species where vaccines must be cost-competitive with antimicrobial treatments. The Quality by Design (QbD) framework (Yu et al., 2014), established in pharmaceutical manufacturing, provides systematic methodology to connect antigen properties with downstream manufacturability, yet its application to reverse vaccinology remains largely unexplored.

This study aimed to: **(1)** sequence and assemble complete genomes of pathogenic

S. iniae isolated from diseased Asian seabass in Thai aquaculture systems; **(2)** apply integrated reverse vaccinology and QbD approaches to identify conserved, immunogenic antigens; and **(3)** classify candidates by manufacturability criteria aligned with multiple production platforms. Using isolate SIKU01 for complete genome assembly and *in silico* screening, we developed an "omics-to-manufacturing" pipeline that provides a practical framework for developing cost-effective vaccines against *S. iniae* and other economically important aquaculture pathogens.

Methods

1. Bacterial Isolation and Cultivation

Five *Streptococcus iniae* pathogens (designated SIKU01–SIKU05) were isolated from diseased Asian seabass (*Lates calcarifer*) exhibiting clinical signs of streptococcosis disease. All isolates originated from a single farm located in Chachoengsao Province, Thailand. Pure bacterial cultures were maintained in Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) containing 25% glycerol at -80°C for long-term storage and subsequent molecular confirmation and genomic DNA extraction.

2. Genomic DNA Extraction and Sequencing

Genomic DNA extraction from *S. iniae* cells involved cultivating bacteria in TSB to logarithmic phase, followed by cell harvesting and lysis. DNA purification was performed using a column-based method with silica membranes (QIAamp DNA Mini Kit, Qiagen, Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol with minor modifications for Gram-positive bacteria. The bacterial cell pellets were subjected to enzymatic lysis using hen lysozyme (20 mg/mL) and overnight incubation at 37°C to digest the peptidoglycan layer, which is particularly thick in Gram-positive bacteria. Following enzymatic treatment, a detergent-based lysis buffer containing proteinase-K was added to complete cell disruption and protein degradation.

The quality and quantity of extracted DNA were assessed using spectrophotometry (NanoDrop2000, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). High Molecular Weight (HMW) DNA integrity was verified by agarose gel electrophoresis. DNA library preparation and quality control were performed according to standard protocols for Illumina sequencing. Sequencing was performed on the Illumina HiSeq 2000 platform (Illumina, USA) using paired-end 151 bp reads, generating approximately 3 million paired-end reads per sample.

3. Genome Assembly and Quality Control

3.1 De Novo Assembly

Initial quality assessment of raw Illumina paired-end reads was performed using FastQC v0.11.9 ([Andrews, 2010](#)) to evaluate read quality, GC content, and adapter contamination. SeqPurge v2019 ([Sturm et al., 2016](#)) was used to trim adapters and low-quality bases using a sliding window approach, removing bases with quality scores below Q20. *De novo* assembly was conducted with Unicycler v0.4.9 ([Wick et al., 2017](#)), which employs SPAdes v3.15.2 ([Bankevich et al., 2012](#)) as its assembly algorithm. Resulting assembly graphs were visualized using Bandage v0.8.1 ([Wick et al., 2015](#)) to assess connectivity and identify potential misassemblies. Assembly quality metrics were evaluated using QUILT v5.0.2 ([Quast et al., 2013](#)).

3.2 Reference-Guided Assembly

Multiple reference strains (QMA0248, 89353, SF1) were obtained from NCBI RefSeq (Supplementary Data 13). Reference-guided assembly was performed by mapping trimmed reads to each reference strain genome using Bowtie2 v2.4.4 ([Langmead and Salzberg, 2012](#)) with the ('--fast-local') option. To assess synteny and structural variations across strains, assembly contigs were aligned against all reference genomes using ProgressiveMauve v2.4.0 ([Darling et al., 2010](#)).

3.3 Reference-Guided De Novo Assembly

A hybrid approach combining *de novo* and reference-guided methods (Lischer and Shimizu, 2017) was employed to improve genome reconstruction for related *S. iniae* strains. Illumina reads were mapped to an intermediate assembly (derived from QMA0248) using Bowtie2 with the ('--end-to-end') option and a quality filter of MAPQ > 10. Variant calling was performed using Pilon v1.23 (Walker et al., 2014), followed by remapping with SNIPPY v4.6.0 (Seemann, 2014), which internally uses BWA-MEM v0.7.17 (Md et al., 2019) for read mapping. CRISPR loci and insertion sequence (IS) regions missing from the reference were recovered from *de novo* assemblies. Each assembly was manually inspected using Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV) v2.9.4 (Robinson et al., 2011) to identify and correct potential assembly errors. Assembly quality was further validated by evaluating read mapping statistics, with >99.7% of reads successfully mapping to the final assemblies, indicating high completeness and accuracy.

4. Technical Validation of Genome Assembly

De novo genome assembly remains a well-known challenge for Illumina-only assemblies due to short read length, missing data, repetitive regions, polymorphisms, and sequencing errors (Lischer and Shimizu, 2017). For genome assembly, we used a hybrid strategy combining *de novo* assembly for CRISPR and missing regions not present in the reference, while the structural backbone of the chromosome originated from mapping to the reference strain QMA0248. IS sequences were reintegrated into the chromosome at their respective positions after retrieving sequences and comparing their accuracy to the ISfinder database (Siguiet et al., 2006) using advanced ab initio methods (Treepong et al., 2018).

To ensure quality and reliability of *S. iniae* genome assemblies for strains SIKU01-05, we implemented multiple validation strategies. Assembly continuity and general statistics were assessed using QUAST v5.3.0, which confirmed high completeness and

contiguity across all five genomes. SIKU01 showed characteristics consistent with high-quality bacterial assemblies, including an expected genome size (2.0 Mb) and GC content of 36.7%. Structural accuracy was evaluated through multi-genome alignments using ProgressiveMauve v2.4.0, revealing strong synteny and no major rearrangements when compared to closely related *S. iniae* strains. Base-level accuracy was confirmed using SNIPPY for short-read realignment and SNP detection, with manual inspection of selected loci using IGV indicating very few variant calls. To assess mapping quality and potential assembly artifacts, Illumina paired-end reads were realigned using Bowtie2, and MAPQ0 loci were examined to screen for high-copy number regions such as insertion sequences. Overall alignment quality was high with minimal problematic genomic loci.

5. Genome Annotation

Genome annotation was first generated with Prokka v1.14.6 (Seemann, 2014) and then standardized before GenBank submission using the NCBI Prokaryotic Genome Annotation Pipeline (PGAP) v4.13 (Li et al., 2021). The assembled chromosome FASTA (Supplementary Data 13) provided the genomic sequence, later joined by locus to supply *Sequence_fna*. The corresponding GenBank feature file (.gb) (Supplementary Data 13) was parsed with a custom BioPython script (Supplementary Code 12) to produce a flat table (Supplementary Data 13) containing one row per gene or CDS feature with coordinates and strand, plus the following qualifiers: *anticodon*, *bound_moiety*, *codon_start*, *db_xref*, *EC_number*, *gene*, *gene_synonym*, *inference*, *locus_tag*, *mol_type*, *ncRNA_class*, *note*, *organism*, *product*, *protein_id*, *regulatory_class*, *rpt_family*, *rpt_type*, *rpt_unit_range*, *rpt_unit_seq*, *strain*, *translation*, *transl_table*.

For convenience, we retained the core fields: *Locus_tag*, *Locus*, *Start*, *End*, *Strand*, *Gene*, *Gene_synonym*, *Product*, *EC_number*, *Codon_start*, *Transl_table*, *Translation*, *Inference*, *Note*, *Protein_id*, *CDSno*. A simple coordinate index (Supplementary Data 13) contributed *Start*, *End*, *Strand*, and *Locus*. The predicted proteome (Supplementary Data 13) supplied the amino acid sequences used for similarity search and do-

main annotation.

6. Functional Annotation and Epitope Detection

For homology transfer, the SIKU01 proteome was aligned against a UniProtKB reference proteome (Supplementary Data 13) using DIAMOND BlastP (Buchfink et al., 2014) with identity threshold $\geq 90\%$ and E-value threshold $\leq 1e-10$, available in the python script (Supplementary Code 12). Hits were captured in Supplementary Data 13 with *query_id*, *subject_id*, *pct_identity*, *aln_length*, *mismatches*, *gap_openings*, *query_start*, *query_end*, *subject_start*, *subject_end*, *evaluate*, and *bit_score*. We parsed *subject_id* to recover *Entry_name* for downstream joins to UniProtKB.

Functional domain and Gene Ontology (GO) evidence were obtained by running InterProScan v5.48-83.0 (Blum et al., 2021) on Supplementary Data 13, integrating multiple databases including Pfam (Mistry et al., 2021), SMART (Letunic et al., 2021), TIGRFAMs (Li et al., 2021), SUPERFAMILY (Pandurangan et al., 2019), Gene3D, CDD, PANTHER, ProSite, TMHMM, Hamap, and FunFam. The resulting General Feature File (Supplementary Data 13) was parsed into Supplementary Data 13 containing *Locus_tag*, *Sequence_MD5_digest*, *Sequence_length*, *Analysis_method*, *Signature_accession*, *Signature_description*, *Start_location*, *Stop_location*, *Score*, *Status*, *Date*, *InterPro_annotations_accession* (IPR), *InterPro_annotations_description*, and *GO_annotations*.

Curated protein-level annotations were integrated from a UniProtKB TSV export (Supplementary Data 13), providing comprehensive functional information including Entry/Entry Name, Protein names, Gene Names, Function [CC], Catalytic activity, Cofactor, Activity regulation, EC number, Pathway, Kinetics, pH dependence, Site, Redox potential, Rhea ID, Temperature dependence, PubMed ID, Keywords/Keyword ID, Protein families, Gene Ontology (GO) and sub-ontologies with GO IDs, Subcellular location [CC], Signal peptide, Transmembrane, Topological domain, Coiled coil, Helix, Beta strand, Turn, Motif, Domain [CC]/Domain [FT], Region, Repeat, Zinc finger, Disulfide bond, Modified residue, Lipidation, Propeptide, Initiator methionine, Caution,

Comments, Annotation, and Features. These were mapped to SIKU01 via *Entry_name* derived from DIAMOND subjects after one-to-one matching between isolate SF1 from UniProtKB reference proteome and isolate SIKU01 (Supplementary Data 13).

Pathway and hierarchy assignments utilized KEGG Mapper/BRITE (Kanehisa, 2000), and GO terms followed the Gene Ontology framework (The Gene Ontology Consortium, 2021) (Supplementary Data 13–13). Transmembrane helices and bacterial Gram-positive N-terminal signal peptides were predicted with TMHMM v2.0 (Krogh et al., 2001) and SignalP v5.0 (Almagro Armenteros et al., 2019), respectively (Supplementary Data 13 and 13). Additional family/domain calls from InterPro’s member databases (Blum et al., 2021) were considered where present.

An epitope evidence layer (Supplementary Data 13–13) was merged on the variable *Locus_tag*, carrying *evaluate_epitope_prediction*, *pct_identity_epitope_prediction*, and *bit_score_epitope_prediction* for matches to curated *Streptococcus* spp. epitopes retrieved from the Immune Epitope Database (IEDB) (Vita et al., 2019) and aligned to the *S. iniae* proteome with DIAMOND BlastP (Buchfink et al., 2014) (Supplementary Code 12). Epitope hits were retained at $E \leq 1 \times 10^{-3}$ (observed range 10^{-3} to 10^{-16}) (Supplementary Data 13).

7. Protein-Level Biophysical Descriptors

Protein-level biophysical descriptors were computed from amino acid sequences using the Peptides R package (Osorio et al., 2015) and a custom script to annotate SIKU01 proteins of the proteome (Supplementary Code 12) and the SeqinR package in R (Charif and Lobry, 2007) from translated protein sequences in Supplementary Data 13. For each protein, we recorded theoretical isoelectric point (*pI*), molecular weight (*MW*), net charge at pH 6.8, 7.0, and 7.4, GRAVY-like hydrophobicity, aliphatic index, instability index, Boman binding potential, predicted membrane propensity class, and sequence length (aa). These descriptors fed Matrix-1 filters (solubility, stability, manufacturability biases) and Matrix-2 platform compatibility rules. Physicochemical descriptors

were appended as *Charge_pH_6_8*, *Charge_pH_7*, *Charge_pH_7_4*, *aliphatic_Index*, *hydrophobicity*, *instability_index*, *binding_potential*, *length_AA*, *mw*, and *pI* to a subset of UniProtKB TSV data (Supplementary Data 13), summarizing SIKU01 physicochemical properties of individual proteins (Supplementary Data 13).

8. PubMed Literature Search

PubMed literature and PMID metadata were retrieved using a custom R script (Supplementary Code 12). Proteins with prior experimental mentions, particularly as vaccine candidates or virulence factors, received graduated positive scoring based on evidence strength (Supplementary Data 13).

9. Annotation Merging and Biophysical Analysis

All previous annotation layers were merged using (Supplementary Code 12) a custom script made for that purpose while for manual curation, cross-checking UniProtKB keywords/feature texts with InterPro domain calls, KEGG/GO assignments, and primary PGAP/Prokka annotations to produce the combined initial table used in downstream QbD scoring (Supplementary Data 15). Plots and distributions were generated using a custom R script (Supplementary Code 12).

10. Pangenomics and Sequence Conservation Analysis

Ninety representative *S. iniae* genomes obtained from NCBI Genomes (listed in Supplementary Data 14) were annotated using Prokka (Seemann, 2014) to homogenize coding sequence (CDS) annotations prior to graph-based pan-genome clustering with Panaroo (Tonkin-Hill et al., 2020b), which implements an improved orthology graph algorithm originally inspired by Roary (Page et al., 2015b). Clustering was performed at high amino acid identity threshold ($\geq 85\%$), with a core gene inclusion cutoff of 95%, and paralogs excluded. This graph-based ortholog clustering produced Supplementary Data 14, including a gene presence/absence (P/A) table and summary links for each gene

sequence and annotation used in parsing the final pangenome graph.

To annotate each genome with consistent pan-genome metadata, we used a custom Python script (Supplementary Code 12), adapted from `post_run_gff_output.py`, a Panaroo-based utility. This script integrated Panaroo's graph and table outputs to reconstruct isolate-specific GFF3 annotation files containing standardized pangenome attributes. The Rtab file served as quantitative input to determine gene carriage frequency across isolates and to assign each orthogroup to a pangenome class (core, soft-core, shell, or cloud) based on prevalence thresholds: $\geq 99\%$ for core, 95–98% for soft-core, 15–94% for shell, and $< 15\%$ for cloud. These classifications generated augmented presence/absence tables linking each Panaroo cluster ID to its class, representative gene, and genome distribution.

To derive isolate-specific orthogroups, we extracted *S. iniae* SIKU01 clusters from Panaroo tables using a custom script (Supplementary Code 12), which filtered the pangenome Rtab file to produce Supplementary Data 14. This dataset was enriched with GFF-derived attributes using (Supplementary Code 12), another custom script which cross-referenced *pangenome_id* entries against the Panaroo-generated GFF file to create a unified annotation table. Although biased toward the SIKU01 reference isolate, this approach provided one-to-one mapping between pangenome clusters and genome-specific locus tags, enabling precise tracking of orthogroups during downstream conservation analysis.

For each genome, CDS and translated protein sequences were extracted from annotated GFF3 files using `gffread` (Pertea and Pertea, 2020), and all orthologous sequences were concatenated into two tagged FASTA files with `SeqKit` (Shen et al., 2016). These combined FASTA files were processed by a custom Python pipeline (Supplementary Code 12), which automatically retrieved sequences by cluster ID and performed per-cluster multiple sequence alignments (MSAs) with `MAFFT` (Katoh et al., 2002) or `Clustal Omega` (Sievers and Higgins, 2018) depending on cluster size. The resulting nucleotide- and amino acid-level MSAs formed the foundation for subsequent analyses

of sequence variability, conservation, and structure-based mapping.

All MSAs were analyzed in R (Supplementary Code 12) using a custom script, which calculated normalized Shannon entropy ($H.norm$) at both codon and amino acid levels via the Bio3D R package (Grant et al., 2006). For each orthogroup, $H.norm$ quantified sequence conservation on a continuous scale from 0 (fully conserved) to 1 (maximally variable). Antigens with median $H.norm \leq 0.05$ were classified as highly conserved, while those above 0.90 were excluded as excessively variable. These conservation metrics, together with gene-carriage data from Panaroo, defined the gene-carriage and sequence-variability components of the Quality-by-Design (QbD) framework (Pre-M1 and M1 matrices) (Supplementary Data 14).

11. Protein Structure Prediction and Visualization

Three-dimensional structures of prioritized *S. iniae* antigens (GAPDH, enolase, GroEL, Sortase A) were predicted using AlphaFold2 (Jumper et al., 2021) and cross-validated against available homologous templates in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (Berman, 2000). Predicted PDB files were examined in UCSF ChimeraX v1.6 (Meng et al., 2023) for fold integrity, residue geometry, and solvent accessibility.

To quantify site-specific structural conservation, we implemented a per-residue identity analysis (Supplementary Code 12) that scanned each aligned FASTA previously produced by MAFFT. For every alignment, the script compared all sequences to the reference (first entry) and recorded, for each residue position, the number and percentage of identical residues across all genomes. These per-site identity profiles were mapped onto AlphaFold2 models in ChimeraX using custom color scripts to generate gradient-based visualizations where blue indicated highly conserved residues and red denoted variable positions. This approach provided a direct link between MSA entropy ($H.norm$) values and 3D spatial conservation, highlighting structurally stable and immunologically relevant regions.

Epitope localization was performed using (Supplementary Code 12), a custom Python script which scanned PDB chains for exact matches to epitope peptide sequences identified by IEDB mapping. For each hit, the script reported the model ID, chain ID, and PDB residue range corresponding to the matched peptide, enabling precise overlay of B- and T-cell epitopes onto predicted antigen structures. Surface visualization and electrostatic potential mapping were carried out in ChimeraX using "surface color" and "cartoon" representations to assess accessibility and topological context.

12. Codon Adaptation Index (CAI) and Expression Compatibility

Codon usage frequencies for target organisms were obtained from the Kazusa Codon Usage Database (Holcomb et al., 2019), available at <https://www.kazusa.or.jp/codon/>. Species-specific codon frequency tables were downloaded (Supplementary Data 15), providing frequencies per thousand codons for each organism's coding sequences. **The Codon Adaptation Index (CAI)** quantifies the degree of preference for synonymous codons in a given organism, where values range from 0 (least preferred) to 1 (most preferred).

For each amino acid family, the relative adaptiveness of codon i was calculated as $w_i = f_i / f_{max}$, where f_i represents the frequency per thousand of codon i for its amino acid and f_{max} represents the frequency per thousand of the most frequently used codon for that amino acid. For example, proline codons in *Oreochromis niloticus* were calculated as follows: CCG had $w_i = 7.39/16.53 = 0.447$, CCA had $w_i = 14.59/16.53 = 0.883$, CCT had $w_i = 16.53/16.53 = 1.000$ (optimal), and CCC had $w_i = 14.91/16.53 = 0.902$. The value 16.53 represents the highest frequency among all proline codons, making CCT the optimal reference codon.

For complete gene sequences, CAI was computed as the geometric mean of rel-

ative adaptiveness values using the formula:

$$CAI = \left(\prod_{k=1}^L w_k \right)^{1/L}$$

where the product encompasses all L sense codons in the gene sequence. Stop codons (UAA, UAG, UGA) and the single methionine codon (AUG) were excluded from CAI calculations as they lack synonymous alternatives for optimization.

13. Quality by Design (QbD) Framework

To implement QbD principles effectively within the reverse vaccinology framework, specific criteria were established to guide systematic antigen selection. These criteria served as the foundation for developing a quantitative scoring matrix computed in a custom script (Supplementary Code 12) that ensures both immunological efficacy and manufacturing feasibility.

13.1 QbD Design Space: Gene Carriage (Matrix Pre-M1)

The gene carriage design space defines the level of genomic conservation of an antigen across the *S. iniae* pangenome. This Critical Quality Attribute (CQA) prioritizes stable and widely distributed antigens to prevent loss of vaccine efficacy in heterologous strains. Based on the pan-genome presence/absence matrix, the core genome (present in $\geq 99\%$ of isolates) was retained whereas soft-core genome (95–98%), shell (15–94%), and cloud (<15%) genes were excluded from further evaluation. This filtering yielded 1,538 core and 110 soft-core genes (Supplementary Data 15), forming the foundation for downstream antigen variability and QbD scoring due to their broad distribution and genetic stability.

13.2 QbD Design Space: Amino Acid and Nucleotide Variability (Matrix 1)

The normalized Shannon entropy (*H.norm*) defined the antigen variability design space, quantified from per-cluster MSAs. Each residue received two complementary measures: (1) *H.norm* from sequence alignments (0 = fully conserved, 1 = maximally variable) and (2) percent identity (*%ID*) relative to the amino acid reference sequence (SIKU01). These values were averaged per gene to yield gene-wise conservation indices subsequently integrated into the QbD variability matrix (M1) (Supplementary Data 15). Genes with median *H.norm* ≤ 0.05 and mean *%ID* $\geq 95\%$ were prioritized as structurally and functionally stable antigens. Residues with low entropy and high surface exposure (as confirmed by ChimeraX mapping) defined the structural conservation-driven QbD design space, used to constrain antigen selection and ensure manufacturing consistency across *S. iniae* lineages.

13.3 QbD Design Space: General Physicochemical and Expression Characteristics (Matrix 1)

The protein length design space favors candidates with 100 or more amino acids to ensure sufficient epitope diversity while avoiding overly short sequences that lack functional relevance. Proteins containing 50–99 amino acids are classified as too short and excluded due to instability concerns, while those with fewer than 50 amino acids face exclusion for insufficient immunogenic potential.

Molecular weight constraints target the 20–80 kDa range to balance immune system interaction with proper folding capabilities, with the optimal 20–50 kDa range receiving highest priority for *E. coli* expression systems.

The isoelectric point (*pI*) design space recognizes multiple optimal ranges depending on purification strategy. Proteins with *pI* values between 4.0–7.5 receive priority due to superior solubility characteristics and broad purification platform compatibility. The *pI* range of 7–9 provides negative charge under physiological conditions,

facilitating purification via histidine tag chromatography or silicon dioxide-based filters as specified in the foundational selection criteria. Additionally, proteins with *pI* values between 2–4 offer specialized advantages for silica-based purification systems through enhanced electrostatic interactions.

Hydrophobicity design space assessment relies on the GRAVY index, which prioritizes proteins within the -0.5 to +0.5 range to minimize aggregation tendencies and support aqueous solubility throughout the manufacturing process.

Protein stability design space relies on the **instability index (II)** calculated from primary sequence data, with values of 40 or lower indicating favorable *in vivo* stability characteristics.

Literature support provides empirical validation through PubMed literature and PMID, with proteins having prior experimental mentions, particularly as vaccine candidates or virulence factors, receiving graduated positive scoring based on evidence strength.

13.4 QbD Design Space: Immunogenicity (Matrix 1)

Epitope prediction analysis identifies the presence of known sequences that stimulate T and B lymphocytes, considering the 30% similarity between fish and human immunoglobulins in the scoring framework. Proteins predicted to contain both T- and B-cell epitopes (inferred from IEDB) receive maximum immunological relevance scoring, while those lacking predicted epitopes face penalty assessment.

13.5 QbD Design Space: Host-specific Expression (Matrix 1 – CAI)

In vitro expression efficiency design space prediction utilizes the **Codon Adaptation Index (CAI)** to assess translational compatibility with *E. coli* systems, following the principle of optimal codon usage for maximizing protein expression. Top-

quartile CAI values receive positive weighting, while bottom-quartile scores indicate potential expression difficulties (Supplementary Data 15–15).

13.6 QbD Design Space: Matrix 2 – Secondary Selection

In Matrix 2, candidate antigens from Matrix 1 were screened multiple times for compatibility with specific downstream purification modalities by aligning their intrinsic molecular descriptors with platform-specific Critical Process Parameters (CPPs). Five distinct sets of design spaces were evaluated: silica affinity, cellulose affinity, ion exchange chromatography (anion exchange (AEX) and cation exchange (CEX)), and plasmid DNA (pDNA) expression. This pre-downstream design space cross-references *in silico* Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) with platform-specific CPPs to ensure process-antigen compatibility before physical development for maximum cost-efficiency post-biomanufacturing (Supplementary Data 15–15).

Silica Affinity Purification: Silica-based purification technologies offer ubiquity, low cost, and adaptability across laboratory and industrial bioprocessing applications. Critical material attributes (CMAs) include silanol density, surface topology, and functionalization chemistry, while key CPPs encompass pH, ionic strength, and buffer composition (Supplementary Data 15). Affinity tags with high silica specificity, including Si-tag, SB7, Car9, R5, and the synthetic octapeptide (RH)4, composed of four repeating Arginine-Histidine units, interact through electrostatic and hydrogen-bonding mechanisms with silanol-rich matrices. Proteins presenting net positive charge at pH 7.4 demonstrate enhanced adsorption due to electrostatic attraction to partially deprotonated silanol groups ($\equiv\text{Si-OH} \rightarrow \equiv\text{Si-O}^-$). QbD selection criteria required $pI > 4$ and a surface-exposed cationic patch at loading pH (offered by the fusion of a silica binding peptide short tag). Elution is achieved by increasing pH from 7.4 to 8.5, expanding silanol deprotonation and reducing hydrogen-bond donor capacity. Short tag lengths (7–20 aa) were favored to avoid steric hindrance and folding interference (Supplementary Data 15).

Cellulose Affinity Purification: Cellulose-based purification uses cellulose-binding modules (CBMs) such as CBM3, CBM9, or CelD, which recognize repeating β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-D-glucopyranose units through hydrogen bonding with hydroxyl groups and hydrophobic stacking with planar glucan rings. Key CPPs include buffer pH (6.0–8.5), salt concentration, cellulose type, and contact time. Since binding is mediated by the CBM domain rather than antigen charge properties, no *pI* requirement was applied. However, CBMs add substantial polypeptide segments (30–200 aa), necessitating length constraints. Antigens were preferentially kept ≤ 400 aa to ensure total fusion constructs remained ≤ 430 – 630 aa, limiting metabolic burden, misfolding risk, and aggregation while preserving tag accessibility (Supplementary Data 15).

Ion Exchange Chromatography (IEX): Ion exchange utilizes the net charge of a protein to separate it from other proteins. Based on the type of resins and the charge of the protein, anion exchange chromatography or cation exchange chromatography techniques may be used. Anion exchange chromatography was modeled on quaternary amine functional groups (e.g., $-\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_3)_3$) binding negatively charged proteins through electrostatic interaction with deprotonated carboxyl groups. The QbD filter retained proteins with $pI \leq 6.5$ and net charge ≤ -1 at pH 7.4 (Supplementary Data 15). Cation exchange chromatography employed sulfonate ligands ($-\text{SO}_3^-$) that bind protonated amines from Lys, Arg, and His side chains. Selection criteria favored proteins with $pI \geq 8.0$ and net charge $\geq +1$ at pH 7.4, ensuring positive charge under working conditions for effective resin binding (Supplementary Data 15).

Plasmid DNA Expression: Plasmid DNA expression was treated as a distinct design space, optimizing antigens for high-yield, high-fidelity eukaryotic expression in DNA vaccine formats. Sequence-level CQAs included GC3 enrichment to improve mRNA stability and translation efficiency, ORF length threshold (set at the median coding sequence length of core genes ≈ 2.2 kb), and complete absence of internal Type IIS restriction sites (BsaI, BsmBI, Eco31I) to ensure seamless Golden Gate Assembly cloning compatibility (Supplementary Data 15–15).

14. Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.2.0. Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (ρ) were calculated using the `cor()` function along with option `method="spearman"`. Statistical significance of correlations was assessed using the `rcorr()` function from the `Hmisc` package, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. For the correlation between hydrophobicity and aliphatic index ($\rho = 0.82$, $p < 10^{-15}$), significance was calculated using `cor.test()`. While no formal corrections for multiple testing were applied in this exploratory analysis, we note that key correlations (e.g., hydrophobicity-aliphatic index, $\rho = 0.82$) would remain significant even after Bonferroni correction.

Kernel density estimation was performed using the `density()` function with 512 interpolation points. Density contours in scatter plots were generated using `ggplot2`'s `stat_density_2d()` with default bandwidth selection. All histograms used 50 bins for consistency across distributions.

Normalized Shannon entropy for sequence conservation was calculated for proteins present in at least 95% of genomes as $H = -\sum(p_i \times \log_2(p_i))$, where p_i is the frequency of amino acid i at each position. Normalized entropy (H_{norm}) was calculated as $H/\log_2(20)$ to scale values between 0 (fully conserved) and 1 (maximum variation), using the `Bio3D` R package ([Grant et al., 2006](#)).

Quartile thresholds for codon adaptation index (CAI) and GC3 content were calculated using `quantile()` at probabilities 0.25 and 0.75. All thresholds were calculated on the Pre-M1 filtered dataset ($n=1,374$ proteins) to ensure consistency across platforms.

For multimodal distribution detection, hierarchical density-based clustering (HDBSCAN) was applied with `minPts=40` using the `dbscan` package. Statistical summaries (mean, median, standard deviation) were calculated for all biophysical properties. The dataset M0 comprising the full SIKU01 proteome ($N = 1,855$ proteins) (Supplementary

Data 15) and the Pre-M1 filtered subset ($n = 1,374$ proteins) (Supplementary Data 15) provided adequate statistical power for correlation analyses.

Results

1. Genome Assembly and Annotation Results

1.1 Genome Assembly of *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01

We assembled a complete, circular genome of *S. iniae* strain SIKU01 (2.09 Mb, 37% GC) with high completeness and no plasmids detected (Figs. 27a–b); Appendix Figure 33). Whole-genome comparisons with reference *S. iniae* strains QMA0248 (Alsheikh-Hussain *et al.*, 2022), 89353 (Gong *et al.*, 2017), SF1 (Zhang *et al.*, 2014b), and LSSM211007Si confirmed strong macrosyntenic conservation (Fig. 27c–d). We also analyzed synteny relative to the original Amazon dolphin isolate QMA0141 from 1976 (Pier and Madin, 1976) (Appendix Figure 34).

1.2 Functional Annotation of *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01

Annotation of strain SIKU01 identified 2,004 genes, including 1,855 protein-coding sequences and 77 RNAs (Supplementary Data 13). Functional classification with InterProScan (Quevillon *et al.*, 2005), KEGG Mapper (Kanehisa and Sato, 2020), and Gene Ontology (GO) (Ashburner *et al.*, 2000) (Supplementary Data 13–13) revealed a broad repertoire of metabolic enzymes, transporters, DNA-repair proteins, and cell-surface factors, along with subsets of stress-response proteins, toxins, and antimicrobial resistance determinants (Figure 27e). This comprehensive genome annotation provided the foundation for proteome-wide reverse vaccinology and subsequent Quality-by-Design (QbD) manufacturability screening of candidate vaccines (Supplementary Data 15–15).

Figure 27 Complete genome assembly and functional annotation of *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01. **(a)** Genome assembly and reference-guided workflow from raw reads to validated circular chromosome. **(b)** Assembly and annotation statistics, including genome size, GC content, gene counts, and RNA features. **(c)** Comparative macro-synteny of SIKU01 against public *S. iniae* reference strains, showing conserved genomic architecture. **(d)** Metadata of strain SIKU01 and related isolates, including collection date, country, and host species, used in hybrid reference-guided assembly. **(e)** Functional annotation of the SIKU01 proteome, including KEGG Mapper categories, Gene Ontology subcellular localization, and InterProScan domain assignments.

2. Reverse Vaccinology Results

2.1 Reverse Vaccinology and Identification of Antigenic Epitopes

Rather than proposing a single antigen, this reverse vaccinology framework operationalizes vaccine candidate evaluation through standardized QbD manufacturability and immunogenicity filters. Using the annotated SIKU01 proteome (N = 1,855 proteins, Supplementary Data 13), we applied reverse vaccinology (Liu [et al.](#), 2009; Moriel [et al.](#), 2010; Rawal [et al.](#), 2021) to identify antigens with extracellular or surface localization signals and to detect B- and T-cell epitopes by mapping DIAMOND BlastP (Buchfink [et al.](#), 2021) hits to immunogenic epitopes from the Immune Epitope Database (IEDB) (Supplementary Data 13–13). Epitope matches were retained at $E \leq 1 \times 10^{-3}$ (range 10^{-3} to 10^{-16}) (Vita [et al.](#), 2025). This yielded 17 epitope-positive proteins (Table 9), including classical streptococcal targets previously validated in experimental studies (Dale [et al.](#), 2017; Dobrut [et al.](#), 2018; Elfaitouri [et al.](#), 2013; Fourie and Wilson, 2020; Kolberg [et al.](#), 2006). These 17 epitope-containing, QbD-prioritized proteins were then evaluated for their antigenic conservation across 90 representative *S. iniae* genomes obtained from NCBI Genomes (Supplementary Data 14), revealing heterogeneous conservation patterns among predicted surface-exposed and virulence-associated antigens (Appendix Figure 35). Highly conserved targets included enolase, GAPDH, and the 60 kDa chaperonin GroEL, while other proteins exhibited greater presence/absence patterns, indicating lower gene carriage across strains. These annotated epitope-containing antigens were subsequently carried forward, along with the full SIKU01 proteome, into the QbD manufacturability funnel (Figure 28).

3. Quality By Design Results

3.1 CQAs and CPPs in the QbD Framework

In Quality by Design (QbD), Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) describe the antigen or plasmid properties that determine safety, efficacy, and manufacturabil-

Table 9 Predicted antigenic epitopes from *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01. Seventeen proteins were identified by DIAMOND searches against the IEDB database ($E \leq 1 \times 10^{-3}$) and are shown with their locus tags in SIKU01, UniProtKB annotations for gene name, and matched amino acid epitope sequences with cross-homology to IEDB database.

Locus Tag	Subject ID (Gene Name in UniProtKB)	Epitope Sequence (Amino Acid)
SIKU01_001181	Enolase	RAAADYLEVPLYNYLG
SIKU01_001378	metal binding protein of ABC transporter (lipoprotein)	EINTEEEGTPDQISSLIEK
SIKU01_001395	cell envelope proteinase A	LYIKAIEDAVALGADAINLS
SIKU01_001681	pneumococcal histidine triad protein D	YVTSHGDHYHYNGKVPYDA
SIKU01_001709	immunogenic secreted protein	DASGTGKRRAEVMEKLDQWIDRHGGTP
SIKU01_001765	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	MVVKVGVINGFGFRIGRLAFRRIQ
SIKU01_001769	surface exclusion protein	VMLTAVGLTGFKLKKDIK
SIKU01_001890	M protein	QLPSTGDSYNPFFTASAMAI
SIKU01_001902	GroEL	LPTLVLNKIRGTFNVVAVKAPGFGDRRKAM
SIKU01_001991	Inosine-5'-monophosphate dehydrogenase [<i>S. agalactiae</i>]	VVKVGIGPGSIC
SIKU01_001995	conserved hypothetical protein	AQNLRNILHGSDSIFYTFTS
SIKU01_000047	Amidase	EEKQAANQEAINVA
SIKU01_000165	DNA-directed RNA polymerase subunit β' [<i>S. pyogenes</i>]	IDNGRRRGPITGP
SIKU01_000216	pneumococcal histidine triad protein D	YVTSHGDHFHFYNGKVPYDA
SIKU01_000259	YSIRK signal domain / LPXTG anchor domain surface protein	GVNQFIPFELFGDGMRLRL
SIKU01_000404	trigger factor	ELDDELAKDIDEEV
SIKU01_000973	hypothetical protein SPy1154	DSVLEAQMASQQLPVIGGIA

ity, while Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) define the thresholds, ranges, or decision rules imposed on those attributes to ensure the product meets quality for cost-efficient purification through various common downstream manufacturability routes (Yu et al., 2014). These include pDNA in two target hosts (zebrafish and Nile tilapia) (Kutzler and Weiner, 2008), or recombinant protein expressed in *E. coli* as bio-factories (Francis and Page, 2010; Rosano and Ceccarelli, 2014) where affinity-purified proteins are modified with silica-binding peptides (Freitas et al., 2022; Spriestersbach et al., 2015) or CBMs (Carrard et al., 2000), while unmodified proteins are recovered by ion-exchange (Duong-Ly and Gabelli, 2014).

3.2 Definition of Design Spaces (DS)

We integrated the immunoinformatic dataset into a QbD framework that links immunological relevance with manufacturability (Table 10). For *S. iniae* SIKU01 antigens, the Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) included expression and annotation fea-

tures (the coding sequence (CDS) must encode a complete open reading frame (ORF) (Tatusova [et al.](#), 2016), and the gene must be present in the core pangenome (Page [et al.](#), 2015a; Tatusova [et al.](#), 2016; Tettelin [et al.](#), 2008; Tonkin-Hill [et al.](#), 2020a)), sequence and structural properties (protein length (aa) (Bachmann and Jennings, 2010a), molecular weight (MW) (Bachmann and Jennings, 2010a), hydrophobicity by GRAVY (Kyte and Doolittle, 1982), instability index (II) (Guruprasad [et al.](#), 1990; Scheiblhofer [et al.](#), 2017), isoelectric point (pI) (Widmann [et al.](#), 2010), and net electrostatic charge (z) of the folded protein in aqueous solution at pH 7 (Zayas, 1997)), conservation (normalized Shannon entropy (H.norm) (Grant [et al.](#), 2021; Strait and Dewey, 1996), from multiple-sequence nucleotide alignments), translational potential (codon adaptation index (CAI) (Francis and Page, 2010; Holcomb [et al.](#), 2019; Zhou [et al.](#), 2016), in *E. coli*, zebrafish and Nile tilapia), gene characteristics (GC3 fraction [0–1] (Sémon [et al.](#), 2005; Vinogradov, 2005), gene length (nt) (Bachmann and Jennings, 2010a; Vita [et al.](#), 2025), and Type IIS sites (count) (Bird [et al.](#), 2022a; Marillonnet and Grutzner, 2020)), and external evidence (PubMed literature (PMID), IEDB (peptide) data (Vita [et al.](#), 2025)) Table 9). Route-specific descriptors, such as silica-binding peptide length (20 aa) (Freitas [et al.](#), 2022; Spriestersbach [et al.](#), 2015) and cellulose-binding module length (\approx 30–200 aa) (Carrard [et al.](#), 2000), although not scored, were also included as CQAs.

- **M0 (mandatory inclusion).** At this stage, candidates were retained only if the CDS encoded a protein and the ORF was full-length; sequences failing these requirements were excluded.
- **Pre-M1 (mandatory inclusion).** At this stage, candidates were retained only if they were present in the core genome fraction of the pangenome. Any sequence failing these requirements was excluded.
- **M1 (general filters).** Retain if protein length 100–699 aa (Bachmann and Jennings, 2010a); conservation H.norm > 0.98 (mandatory); molecular weight (MW) 20–60 kDa (+2, else 0); literature support (+1, none = 0); IEDB (peptide) present (+3, none = 0).

- **M1 (protein route).** Host-specific CAI in *E. coli*, CAI_{ec} (+2 top quartile / -2 bottom quartile / 0 otherwise); hydrophobicity (GRAVY -0.5 to +0.5) +2; instability index (II) ≤ 40 +1 ([Guruprasad et al., 1990](#)).
- **M1 (pDNA routes).** Host-specific CAI in zebrafish (CAI_{dr}) or tilapia (CAI_{on}) scored identically (+2 top quartile / -2 bottom quartile / 0 otherwise).
- **M2 (downstream manufacturability, platform specific).** In the final stage, manufacturability descriptors were applied. For silica affinity, net charge (z) at pH 7 was used: $z \leq -15$ led to exclusion, $-15 < z \leq -5$ scored -1, $-5 < z \leq +5$ scored +2, and $z > +5$ scored +3 (capped at +3). A soft preference of +1 was also added for proteins with isoelectric points (pI) between 7 and 9. Silica-binding peptides were constrained to 20 aa to minimize metabolic cost. For cellulose affinity, candidate antigens were required to be <400 aa to offset the 30-200 aa carbohydrate-binding module fusion; longer proteins were excluded. For ion-exchange chromatography, anion exchange (AEX) required $pI \leq 6.0$; within this constraint, proteins with z at pH 7 were scored as 0 to -5 (+1), -5 to -15 (+2), and ≤ -15 (+3). Cation exchange (CEX) required $pI \geq 8.0$; within this constraint, proteins with z at pH 7 were scored as 0 to +5 (+1), +5 to +15 (+2), and $\geq +15$ (+3). For plasmid DNA (pDNA) manufacturability, GC3 fraction [0–1] in the top quartile scored +2, the bottom quartile scored -2, and the middle quartiles scored 0. Gene length (nt) shorter than the cohort median scored +1, while longer genes scored 0. Absence of internal Type IIS sites (count = 0) scored +2, while presence scored 0.

Figure 28 summarizes the Quality-by-Design (QbD) lifecycle applied to the *S. iniae* proteome, illustrating how successive filtering stages (M0–M2) progressively refine the antigen candidate space. The workflow integrates antigen design and manufacturability routes through iterative filtering of Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) into Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) across multiple production systems. This staged CQA→CPP mapping and definition of design spaces ensure that retained candidates are both immunologically relevant and manufacturable at scale, accommodating mul-

multiple expression systems (plasmid DNA *in vivo* and recombinant protein vaccines in *E. coli*) as well as diverse downstream purification routes (silica and cellulose affinity, ion-exchange chromatography, and pDNA expression in zebrafish and Nile tilapia). Full thresholds and scoring rules are provided in (Table 10). Complete proteome-level distributions of CQA attributes and their pairwise correlations (Spearman's ρ) are shown in (Appendix Figures 36–38).

Figure 28 Quality-by-Design (QbD) workflow integrating antigen design and manufacturability routes. **(a)** The conceptual QbD lifecycle links the Target Product Profile (TPP), *in silico* antigen scoring, and affinity-tag or plasmid purification strategy through iterative design feedback. **(b)** The M2 manufacturability stage defines platform-specific routes—silica and cellulose affinity, ion-exchange chromatography (AEX/CEX), and plasmid DNA optimization—each translating Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) into measurable Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) for scalable vaccine production. **(c)** The workflow illustrates the progressive narrowing of the vaccine-antigen design space through successive QbD stages (M0 → Pre-M1 → M1 → M2).

3.3 Initial QbD Proteome Reduction (M0 → Pre-M1 → M1-general) Results

At the unfiltered M0 stage (Supplementary Data 15), the proteome (N = 1,855 proteins) spanned a wide biophysical space, with hydrophobicity and isoelectric point distributions showing clear bimodality (Appendix Figure 39a). Applying the Pre-M1 inclusion gate (core genome carriage) reduced the set to 1,374 proteins (Appendix Figure 39b). (Supplementary Data 15). M1-general filters then retained 1,101 proteins by enforcing protein length 100–699 aa (else excluded), conservation (H.norm > 0.98, else excluded), molecular weight (MW) 20–60 kDa (+2 points), literature support (+1 point), and IEDB epitope presence (+3 points) (Appendix Figure 39c). (Supplementary Data 15).

3.4 Platform-specific Gates (M1) Results

Filters were adapted to expression platforms in a host-dependent manner (Appendix Figure 40a). For the M1-protein route in *E. coli* (141 proteins), feasible antigens required CAI_{ec} ≥ Q3, moderate hydrophobicity (GRAVY −0.5 to +0.5), and stability (instability index (II) ≤ 40) (Supplementary Fig. S08a), detailed in (Supplementary Data 15). For the M1-pDNA routes, the only gate was host-specific CAI ≥ Q3, yielding tilapia (207 proteins) and zebrafish (212 proteins) (Appendix Figure 40b-c), detailed in (Supplementary Data 15-15). GC3 and nucleotide length constraints were not applied until M2. In both hosts, density contours showed clustering of survivors within narrow codon usage and sequence length ranges, reflecting platform-specific optimization for translation efficiency and manufacturability.

3.5 Downstream Manufacturability Design Spaces (M2) Results

To evaluate manufacturability, each downstream platform was subjected to stepwise Quality by Design (QbD) filtering (M2 criteria) (Figure 3.5). Mapping antigens into ion-exchange charge space (Figure 3.5) showed that most proteins were acidic at pH 7 and thus compatible with anion exchange (AEX), whereas only a minor frac-

tion were sufficiently basic to survive cation exchange (CEX). This was reflected in the survivor pools (Fig. 3.5), with 98 proteins retained by AEX and only 20 by CEX. Buffer-specific ranges (Figs. 3.5–3.5) confirmed that AEX survivors were stable across nearly all chemistries ($n = 82$ – 98 proteins), while CEX buffers consistently yielded the same restricted set ($n = 20$ proteins). The full antigen lists for AEX and CEX are provided in (Supplementary Data 15-15).

Affinity purification routes imposed distinct orthogonal constraints: cellulose excluded proteins longer than 400 aa (Fig. 3.5), because the CBM fusion tag is itself large and places a metabolic burden on recombinant expression; minimizing the size of the fused antigen reduces energy demand and steric hindrance, thereby improving folding and yield. In contrast, silica affinity (Fig. 3.5) was governed by electrostatic interactions with surface silanol groups: proteins with pI between 7–9 acquire a net positive charge at physiological pH, enabling stable adsorption to negatively charged silica. These filters reduced the pools to 100 cellulose-compatible and 49 silica-compatible proteins, detailed in (Supplementary Data 15-15).

For plasmid DNA (pDNA) platforms, Critical Quality Attribute (CQA) filters were applied separately on a per-host basis. In *O. niloticus* (Figs. 3.5–3.5), genes and their product were first assessed for $CAI \geq Q3$ (0.60), ensuring codon usage was well adapted to the host translation machinery; this retained 188 sequences. Applying $GC3 \geq Q3$ (0.32) halved the pool to 95, as high G/C content at the third codon position improves mRNA stability and reduces metabolic stress. A further antigen length cutoff ($\leq 2,200$ nt) yielded 57 candidates, favoring shorter constructs with reduced transcriptional burden. Finally, genes containing internal Type IIS restriction sites (e.g., *BsaI*, *SapI*) were excluded because these enzymes cut outside their recognition sites, disrupting modular DNA assembly workflows by preventing a one-step cloning in a Golden Gate Assembly. The final Nile tilapia pDNA pool remained at 57 survivors.

In *D. rerio* (Figs. 3.5–3.5), the thresholds were slightly higher ($CAI \geq Q3$ 0.70, $GC3 \geq Q3$ 0.31). Here, 186 proteins passed the CAI filter, 82 remained after the

GC3 filter, 66 after the length filter, and 65 after the Type IIS removal filter. Comprehensive candidate sets for both pDNA platforms (Nile tilapia and zebrafish) are available in (Supplementary Data [15-15](#)).

Overall, the reverse vaccinology–QbD funnel outputs platform-ready short-lists: 98 AEX, 20 CEX, 100 cellulose, 49 silica, and 57–65 pDNA antigens for immediate downstream development.

Figure 28 Manufacturability design spaces across purification platforms. **(a)** Ion-exchange charge space for protein candidates: pI vs. net charge (z) at pH 7. Shaded bands mark the AEX and CEX inclusion regions; vaccine-referenced antigens are labeled. **(b)** Survivors after M2 filtering by platform; bars show unique genes per route with counts and percentages. Only candidates fitting the biophysiochemical criteria for their respective purification pathway are displayed in color bars. This step reflects manufacturability constraints and downstream process optimization in the QbD framework. **(c–d)** Buffer operating pH ranges for AEX (c) and CEX (d). Short tick marks indicate the working pH (range midpoint). **(e–f)** Protein-route survivors per buffer evaluated at the midpoint: AEX rule = base gate passed, net charge (z) at pH 7 \leq 0, and pI \leq pH_{mid}; CEX rule = base gate passed, net charge (z) at pH 7 \geq 0, and pI \geq pH_{mid}. **(g)** Cellulose: antigen length distribution for M2 survivors; dashed line at 400 aa. **(j)** Silica binding peptides favor proteins with moderate pI (7–9) and positive net charge at pH > 7. **(h, k)** pDNA (M2) scatterplots by host: tilapia (h) and zebrafish (k), showing CAI vs. GC3; dashed lines mark dataset thresholds. **(i, l)** pDNA-route survivors passing each manufacturability gate for tilapia (i) and zebrafish (l): CAI \geq threshold, GC3 \geq threshold, length \leq median, and no Type IIS sites (count).

4. Cross-Validation with Literature

We validated our shortlisted antigens against previously tested *S. iniae* vaccine targets reported in multiple hosts, including Channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*) (Wang et al., 2016b), Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) (Kayansamruaj et al., 2017), Olive flounder (*Paralichthys olivaceus*) (Sheng et al., 2018a, 2023), Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) (Membrebe et al., 2016), Mouse (*Mus musculus*) (Wang et al., 2015a), and Turbot fish (*Scophthalmus maximus*) (Zhang et al., 2014a) (Table 11). Among the top-ranked candidates consistently found across purification routes, antigens with demonstrated *in vivo* protection (enolase, GAPDH, and GroEL) were recovered, supporting the predictive accuracy of the QbD framework.

To further assess their suitability, we modeled GAPDH and enolase, two representative antigens, both well-established in the literature. Structural predictions generated using AlphaFold2 (Yang et al., 2023) for *S. iniae* SIKU01 confirmed highly conserved folds and surface-exposed loops (Wang et al., 2017). Several epitope-containing regions identified through reverse vaccinology were surface-accessible ((Figures 29a–c), highlighted in yellow), consistent with prior reports (Gent et al., 2024). These epitopes (Table 9) are suitable for direct incorporation into subunit vaccines or for the design of chimeric multi-epitope constructs (Pumchan et al., 2020), further validating their suitability as vaccine targets. Both enolase (*eno*) and GAPDH (*gap*) displayed epitope-rich regions spatially separated from catalytic or hypervariable sites, reinforcing their accessibility and stability as broad-spectrum candidates.

Figure 29 Structural mapping of variability, epitopes, and active sites in two model *Streptococcus iniae* vaccine candidates. **(a)** Shannon entropy profiles show that two model and well-known antigens of the scientific literature, GAPDH (*gap*) and enolase (*eno*), are largely conserved with limited variable regions. **(b)** GAPDH (336 aa, UniProt [Q7BB80](#)) carries a predicted N-terminal epitope (MVVKVINGFGRIGRLAFRRRIQ) positioned near, but not overlapping with, the active site and adjacent to a region of high nucleotide-level (codon-derived) variability (1–89 % variation). **(c)** Enolase (435 aa, UniProt [T1TFA0](#)) contains a predicted epitope (RAAADYLEV-PLYNYLG) located opposite the active site and spatially separated from five nucleotide-driven hypervariable surface regions (HR1–HR5), indicating stability and accessibility as a vaccine target. Variability values are based on codon-level polymorphisms within the core-genome alignment and projected onto corresponding amino acid positions in the 3-D models for visualization.

DATA AVAILABILITY AND NCBI SUBMISSIONS

Bighead Catfish

The final diploid genome assembly was screened for contamination using the NCBI Foreign Contamination Screen (FCS) ([Astashyn et al., 2024](#)) and submitted following the Vertebrate Genome Project (VGP) naming conventions (<https://github.com/VGP/vgp-assembly>) ([Rhie et al., 2021](#)). The project is registered under NCBI BioProject [PRJNA1132508](#), with BioSample accession [SAMN41769988](#) corresponding to a Thai (male, adult) bighead catfish (isolate: CMAM; TaxID: 35657). Raw sequencing reads are deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA): Nanopore (20% error) — [SRR29723575](#), HiFi — [SRR29723576](#), Hi-C (150PE) — [SRR29723577](#), and Illumina (150PE) — [SRR29723578](#). The final diploid assembly is available in GenBank under accession numbers [JBLWMO000000000](#) (Haplotype 1) and [JBLWMP000000000](#) (Haplotype 2). A complete dataset, including genome assemblies and supporting files, is permanently archived at Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.14826875](https://zenodo.org/record/14826875)).

F1 Hybrid Catfish

The hybrid genome assembly (*Clarias macrocephalus* × *C. gariepinus*) was processed and submitted using the same quality control and standardization workflow as described above. GenBank accessions are [JBLWFY000000000.1](#) and [JBLWFZ000000000.1](#), corresponding to the *C. macrocephalus* and *C. gariepinus* sub-genomes, respectively. Associated records are hosted under NCBI BioProject [PRJNA1153495](#) and BioSample [SAMN43395848](#) (TaxID: 1334085). Raw sequencing reads are Nanopore ([SRR30599638](#)), HiFi ([SRR30599641](#)), Illumina ([SRR30599640](#)), and Hi-C ([SRR30599639](#)). Additional Illumina datasets correspond to female *C. macrocephalus* ([SAMN42503781](#)) and male *C. gariepinus* ([SAMN43548335](#)). The complete F1 hybrid dataset, including assemblies and metadata, is archived at Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.15269601](https://zenodo.org/record/15269601)).

Streptococcus iniae

The *Streptococcus iniae* project is registered under NCBI BioProject [PRJNA933632](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA933632), with BioSample accession [SAMN33244440](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN33244440). Raw sequencing reads are available in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA): Illumina (150PE), 10 FASTQ files across five datasets—[SRR23406918](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406918) (SIKU01), and [SRR23406921](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406921), [SRR23406920](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406920), [SRR23406919](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406919), and [SRR23406922](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406922) for SIKU02–SIKU05. The annotated genome of SIKU01 is deposited in NCBI GenBank under accession [CP121692.1](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/CP121692.1). Supplementary annotation files, intermediate datasets, and related analysis materials are permanently archived at Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/17476104>). All computational tools used in this study are publicly available, and all command-line parameters are specified in the Methods section. Custom scripts used for data processing, proteome annotation, and Quality-by-Design (QbD) manufacturability analysis are provided as **Supplementary Code**, available at Zenodo (see above) and in the Appendix chapter of this document.

Associated Publications

1. *Andres, Q. L. S., Singchat, W., & Srikulnath, K. (2025). Haplotype-Resolved Chromosome-scale Assembly of the Bighead Catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*) Genome.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14826876>
2. *Andres, Q. L. S., Singchat, W., & Srikulnath, K. (2025). Dual Reference Genomes from F1 Hybrids: Phased Assembly of North African Catfish and Bighead Catfish with Hi-C Data.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15269601>
3. *ANDRES, Q. L. S., Uchuwittayakul, A., & Srisapoom, P. (2025). Complete genome and QbD-guided reverse vaccinology for Streptococcus iniae strain SIKU01.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15264953>

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Genomic Insights and Technical Achievements

1. Catfish Genome Assembly

This study presents the first haplotype-resolved genome assemblies of both bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*) and North African catfish (*C. gariepinus*), achieved through sequencing a single F1 hybrid offspring. Despite using identical pipelines and data sources, the bighead catfish subgenome exhibited lower quality metrics (higher base error rates, lower QV) compared to the African subgenome—likely reflecting differences in transposable element content and the inherent assembly challenges of repeat-rich teleost genomes.

Technical validation followed VGP benchmarks using k -mer sizes of 21 (QV analysis), 28 (alignment applications), and 31 (GenomeScope 2.0). While contamination was detected in raw reads by Mash, it was successfully excluded from final assemblies (confirmed by FCS-NCBI and Mash screening). Primary limitations included low sequencing depth (PacBio HiFi <13X, ONT <36X), suboptimal ONT library quality (longest read <134kb), and software-related challenges including tool maintenance and quality control gaps.

The F1 hybrid genome assembly recovered complete genomic sets from both parental species at exceptional quality (QV50-QV60): 27 pseudochromosomes from bighead catfish and 28 from North African catfish, totaling 1.8 Gb with median QV of 55. The assembly achieved 99.35% completeness (21-mer analysis) with over 40 pseudochromosomes assembled to near telomere-to-telomere continuity. All data are available under NCBI BioProject PRJNA115349.

***Streptococcus iniae* Vaccine Development**

This study presents an integrated reverse vaccinology–Quality by Design (QbD) framework for *S. iniae* vaccines, addressing critical needs in aquaculture where annual streptococcal losses exceed USD 1 billion ([Amillano-Cisneros et al., 2025](#); [Defoirdt et al., 2011](#)). By evaluating all 1,855 proteins from strain SIKU01 through manufacturability filters, we reduced the candidate pool by 74–95% before wet-lab validation while retaining previously validated protective antigens. The pipeline yielded platform-specific candidates: 98 for anion-exchange ([Duong-Ly and Gabelli, 2014](#)), 100 for cellulose-affinity ([Carrard et al., 2000](#)), 49 for silica-affinity purification ([Freitas et al., 2022](#)), and 57–65 for plasmid DNA vaccines ([Marillonnet and Grutzner, 2020](#)), including validated antigens enolase and GAPDH (62–80% RPS in previous trials).

The bimodal pI distribution of the *S. iniae* proteome (peaks at 5.5 and 9.0) explains the five-fold higher capture rate of anion-exchange chromatography, providing practical guidance for purification strategy selection. DNA vaccines showed highest efficacy (80–95% RPS), while our *E. coli* expression filters addressed inclusion-body formation through hydrophobicity and stability constraints ([Francis and Page, 2010](#); [Rosano and Ceccarelli, 2014](#)). To address *S. iniae*'s rapid antigenic variation, we restricted candidates to the conserved core genome (n=1,374) with high conservation thresholds (H.norm >0.98). The framework explicitly links antigen discovery to production feasibility, ensuring candidates remain cost-competitive with current antibiotic treatments while providing manufacturing flexibility through alternative affinity tags ([Bachmann and Jennings, 2010b](#); [Woestenenk et al., 2004](#)) and Golden Gate Assembly compatibility ([Bird et al., 2022b](#); [Marillonnet and Grutzner, 2020](#)). Key limitations include incomplete capture of teleost immune complexity through *in silico* prediction, uneven geographic representation in our 90-isolate pangenome, and the need for experimental validation of manufacturing yields.

Overall Conclusions

This study delivers critical genomic resources for Southeast Asian aquaculture through two complementary achievements. First, we generated four high-quality haplotype-resolved reference genomes (three bighead catfish, one North African catfish) using a novel F1 hybrid sequencing approach that exploits 10% nucleotide divergence between parent species. This method offers a cost-effective alternative to trio-sequencing, particularly valuable for hybridized populations where pure parental lines are unavailable.

Second, we developed an integrated reverse vaccinology–QbD framework for *S. iniae* that systematically connects antigen discovery to manufacturing feasibility. By explicitly linking immunological properties with production constraints, our pipeline accelerates translation from genomic data to deployable vaccines while addressing the economic realities of low- to medium-value aquaculture species.

These resources support multiple applications: targeted genetic improvement for economically valuable traits, enhanced study of host-pathogen interactions, conservation genetics for native Mekong populations, and precise CRISPR guide design for future broodstock improvement. The catfish genomes provide essential infrastructure for Thailand’s hybrid catfish industry, while the vaccine development framework offers a template applicable to other aquaculture pathogens where cost constraints and scalability are paramount.

Despite achieving near Telomere-to-Telomere (T2T) continuity for multiple chromosomes, gaps remain in repeat-rich regions. Current transposable element annotation requires additional transcriptomic data for comprehensive functional characterization. These genomes represent single captive individuals; broader sampling is needed to capture population-level diversity. Nevertheless, by supporting more efficient breeding programs and sustainable disease management, these resources contribute directly to UN Sustainable Development Goal 2 (Zero Hunger) and are publicly available through NCBI to benefit the broader research community.

Recommendations

Future studies should: **(1)** implement Quality by Design principles at the earliest stages of vaccine development for streamlined manufacturing; **(2)** integrate multi-omics data to enhance functional annotation of catfish genomes; **(3)** expand to population-level sequencing for pan-genome construction; **(4)** validate long-term efficacy of identified antigens through field trials; **(5)** develop economic models comparing vaccination versus selective breeding strategies for disease resistance.

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Appendix

Figure 30 GenomeScope2.0 profiles for (a) male *C. gariepinus*, (b) female *C. macrocephalus*, and the F1 hybrid catfish at (c) $k=21$ and (d) $k=31$. The hybrid genome shows an intermediate heterozygosity level (1%) and genome size of 1.8 Gb, consistent with contributions from both parental subgenomes. Parental species exhibit 0.056% (*C. macrocephalus*) and 1.56% (*C. gariepinus*) heterozygosity, respectively. BUSCO analyses confirmed assembly completeness and the presence of two subgenomes. Low Illumina coverage ($<20\times$) in parental datasets resulted in broad peaks in panels (a–b).

Figure 31 Comparative synteny and structural variation between the North African catfish (*C. gariepinus*) reference genome (GCA_024256425.2) and the hybrid catfish genome (*fClahyb_Gar*, this study). **(A)** Genome-wide macrosynteny across 28 pseudochromosomes showing conserved collinearity and localized inversions, translocations, and duplications. **(B)** Sequence variation lengths and percentages of genome size, highlighting highly divergent regions. **(C)** Structural variation composition including duplications, translocations, and inversions. **(D)** Variant feature counts (SNPs, indels, CNVs, tandem repeats) showing genome-wide heterogeneity.

Figure 32 Comparative synteny and structural variation between the Bighead catfish (*C. macrocephalus*) Haplotype 1 (GCA_048544425.1) and the hybrid genome (*fClaHyb_Mac*, this study). **(A)** Genome-wide macrosynteny across 27 pseudochromosomes showing extensive collinearity with limited rearrangements. **(B)** Sequence variation profiles showing divergence and insertion–deletion patterns. **(C)** Structural variation composition between parental and hybrid genomes. **(D)** Variant feature counts across all categories, emphasizing SNP dominance and minor structural variants.

Figure 33 Circular genome synteny and quality control overview of the five sequenced *Streptococcus iniae* strains (SIKU01–SIKU05). The Circos plot shows inter-strain genomic alignments, GC content variation, GC skew, and contig connectivity metrics. Outer rings represent genome coordinates, while inner links highlight conserved syntenic regions among isolates, confirming overall structural stability across strains.

Figure 34 Comparative genome synteny of *Streptococcus iniae* strain SIKU01 relative to the original Amazon River dolphin isolate QMA0141 (collected in 1976) (Pier and Madin, 1976). Homologous regions show strong macrosyntenic conservation with limited structural rearrangements, confirming long-term genomic stability across lineages.

Figure 35 Antigenic variation and gene carriage across the 17 proteins carrying predicted epitopes in *Streptococcus iniae* SIKU01. Bar plots show the distribution of antigenic determinants, sequence variability, and cross-strain presence of corresponding loci, indicating conserved immunogenic targets for vaccine development.

Figure 36 Biophysical landscape of the unfiltered SIKU01 proteome (M0), showing distributions of molecular weight, hydrophobicity (GRAVY), isoelectric point (pI), and instability index (II). These parameters establish the baseline design space for subsequent QbD filtering.

Figure 37 Comprehensive annotation of the SIKU01 proteome, integrating InterProScan domains, KEGG KO terms, and amino acid property distributions. The analysis highlights the dominant functional classes and biochemical diversity among proteins.

Figure 38 Spearman correlation matrix across key QbD-related attributes (length, GRAVY, pI, CAI, GC3, II, H.norm, MW, etc.) in the SIKU01 proteome. Strong associations indicate interdependence between biochemical and translational efficiency parameters.

Figure 39 Sequential Quality-by-Design filtering stages from M0 to M1-general, illustrating progressive proteome reduction based on conservation, biophysical constraints, and immunological evidence. Each panel shows surviving antigen counts per stage.

Figure 40 Platform-specific filtering for recombinant protein (*E. coli*) and plasmid DNA (tilapia and zebrafish) routes. Plots show CAI, GRAVY, and GC3 distributions used to select optimal expression candidates per host system.

Figure 41 Summary of reported vaccine types and corresponding relative percent survival (RPS) values across published *S. iniae* immunization studies. Bar plots distinguish DNA, protein, inactivated, and live-attenuated vaccines.

Figure 42 Comparative analysis of reported vaccine efficacy (RPS) by fish species across literature, including Nile tilapia, Japanese flounder, turbot, catfish, and hybrid bass, showing host-dependent immune protection levels.

Figure 43 Comparison of relative percent survival (RPS) between plasmid DNA and protein subunit vaccine platforms across fish species. Results indicate generally higher and more consistent efficacy for DNA-based vaccines.

Table 10 QbD Design Space (DS) criteria for antigen selection in *Streptococcus iniae* reverse vaccinology. Each CQA–CPP pair was classified based on evidence origin (Data = empirical or computational results; Expert = expert-driven or literature-derived judgement). The staged approach (M0–M2) integrates immunological relevance with manufacturability constraints across protein and plasmid DNA routes.

Stage	CQA (attribute)	CPP (criterion / inclusion)	Rationale	Source
M0	CDS, ORF, core gene (SIKU01 proteome)	Must encode valid protein CDS; full-length ORF; present in SIKU01	Ensures genuine protein products and conservation across strains	Data, Expert (Page et al., 2015a ; Tatusova et al., 2016 ; Tonkin-Hill et al., 2020a)
Pre-M1	Core genome filter	Retain only genes present in the core genome fraction	Prioritizes antigens conserved across multiple isolates	Data, Expert (Page et al., 2015a ; Tetelin et al., 2008)
M1 — General	Protein length (aa), MW, H.norm, literature support (PMID), IEDB (epitope)	100–699 aa; 20–60 kDa (+2); H.norm > 0.98; literature +1; IEDB +3	Filters by size, conservation, and prior immunological evidence	Data, Expert (Bachmann and Jennings, 2010a ; Strait and Dewey, 1996 ; Vita et al., 2025)
M1 — Protein (<i>E. coli</i>)	CAIec, GRAVY, II	CAIec top quartile +2 / bottom -2; GRAVY -0.5 to +0.5 (+2); II ≤ 40 (+1)	Optimizes bacterial expression and solubility	Data, Expert (Francis and Page, 2010 ; Guruprasad et al., 1990 ; Kyte and Doolittle, 1982 ; Rosano and Ceccarelli, 2014)
M1 — pDNA (<i>Zebrafish/Tilapia</i>)	CAI _{dr} , CAI _{on}	Top quartile +2 / bottom -2	Improves in-vivo translation efficiency in <i>D. rerio</i> / <i>O. niloticus</i>	Data, Expert (Kutzler and Weiner, 2008 ; Zhou et al., 2016)
M2 — Silica affinity	Net charge (z) at pH 7, SBP length (aa)	$z \leq -15$ exclude; $-5 < z \leq +5$ (+2); $z > +5$ (+3); SBP ≈ 20 aa	Electrostatic adsorption to silanols; minimize fusion burden	Data, Expert (Freitas et al., 2022 ; Spriestersbach et al., 2015)
M2 — Cellulose affinity	Protein length (aa); CBM size (aa)	Antigen <400 aa; CBM 30–200 aa	Balances fusion tag size and protein yield	Expert (Carrard et al., 2000)
M2 — Ion exchange (AEX/CEX)	pI and net charge (z) at pH 7	AEX: pI ≤ 6; CEX: pI ≥ 8	Binding/selectivity governed by charge at working pH	Data, Expert (Duong-Ly and Gabelli, 2014)
M2 — pDNA manufacturability	GC3 [0–1], gene length (nt), Type IIS (count)	GC3 top quartile +2 / bottom -2; length ≤ median +1; Type IIS count = 0 (+2)	Improves mRNA stability/expression, and cloning efficiency	Data, Expert (Bird et al., 2022a ; Marrillonnet and Grutzner, 2020 ; Sémon et al., 2005 ; Vinogradov, 2005)

Table 11 Compiled vaccine studies against *Streptococcus iniae* (and noted cross-challenges). Each row represents a single study arm with: Reference, Antigen, Accession, RPS (%), Pathogen (default *S. iniae* unless specified), Dose (μg or CFU), Route, Type, and Host. RPS = relative percent survival post-challenge. Routes: IP = intraperitoneal; IM = intramuscular; Oral + Imm = oral plus immersion; Immersion as listed by authors. Types: D = DNA; P = protein subunit; I = inactivated (e.g., FKC); L = live attenuated; O = other (e.g., combo, nanocarrier); D + O = DNA plus other (e.g., molecular adjuvant). Abbreviations: FKC = formalin-killed cells; FCA = Freund’s complete adjuvant; CNT = carbon nanotube; BNC = bacterial nanocellulose. Cross-protection entries are labeled with the reported pathogen. Accessions are GenBank/UniProt as provided by the original studies.

Reference	Antigen	Accession	RPS (%)	Pathogen	Dose	Route	Type	Host
(Giovanni et al., 2025)	rC5a	XKE33153.1	30	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	P	Four-finger threadfin
(Giovanni et al., 2025)	rC5a + FKC	XKE33153.1	97.5	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	O (combo)	Four-finger threadfin
(Cao et al., 2023)	rSip	OP434413	35.71	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia
(Cao et al., 2023)	rSip	OP434413	31.58	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia
(Cao et al., 2023)	BNC-rSip	OP434413	67.86	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia
(Cao et al., 2023)	BNC-rSip	OP434413	78.95	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia
(Liu et al., 2023a)	rEno	OP433490	31.03	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia
(Liu et al., 2023a)	rEno	OP433490	36.84	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia
(Liu et al., 2023a)	CNT-rEno	OP433490	68.96	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia
(Liu et al., 2023a)	CNT-rEno	OP433490	73.68	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia
(Sheng et al., 2023)	rMEPIP (PDHA1)	WP_003099247.1	74.07	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 μg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder
(Sheng et al., 2023)	rMEPIG (GAPDH)	ACX85247.1	77.78	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 μg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder

Reference	Antigen	Accession	RPS (%)	Pathogen	Dose	Route	Type	Host
(Sheng et al., 2023)	rPDHA1	WP_003099247.1	66.67	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder
(Sheng et al., 2023)	rGAPDH	ACX85247.1	62.96	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder
(Liu et al., 2019)	pSagH	AAN16978.1	92.6	Serotype I	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder
(Liu et al., 2019)	pSagH	AAN16978.1	90.6	Serotype I	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder
(Liu et al., 2019)	pSagH	AAN16978.1	83.0	Serotype II	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder
(Liu et al., 2019)	pSagH	AAN16978.1	80.7	Serotype II	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder
(Sheng et al., 2018b)	rPDHA1	WP_003099247.1	72.73	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder
(Sheng et al., 2018b)	rPDHA1	WP_003099247.1	75.0	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder
(Sheng et al., 2018b)	rGAPDH	ACX85247.1	63.64	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder
(Sheng et al., 2018b)	rLDH	WP_003099652.1	36.36	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder
(Wang et al., 2016a)	pcENO + pcIL-8	AGM99057.1, KP701473	80.0	<i>S. iniae</i>	25 µg	IM	D + O	Channel catfish
(Zhang et al., 2014a)	rNeu	K710_1941	77.1	<i>S. iniae</i>	30 µg	IP	P	Turbot
(Sun et al., 2013)	pSagE	AF465842.1	95	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder
(Sun et al., 2012)	pCS10 (Sia10 live carrier)	GU458802.1	81	<i>S. iniae</i>	3×10 ⁸ CFU	Oral + Imm	D + O	Japanese flounder
(Sun et al., 2010)	pSia10	GU458802.1	92.3	<i>S. iniae</i>	40 µg	IM	D	Turbot
(Xiong et al., 2023)	FKC (formalin-killed)	–	71.1	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	I	Golden pompano
(Heckman et al., 2022)	Live attenuated (E1-r250)	–	95.0	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia

Reference	Antigen	Accession	RPS (%)	Pathogen	Dose	Route	Type	Host
(Liu et al., 2020)	Live attenuated (YM011)	CP032400	93.3	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia
(Wang et al., 2014)	Live attenuated (Δ srtA)	KC352714	95.5	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia
(Pridgeon and Klesius, 2011)	Live attenuated (ISNO)	GCA_000648555.1	95	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia
(Buchanan et al., 2005)	Live attenuated (Δ PGM)	AY846302	90–100	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Hybrid striped bass

Table 12 Each script is cited in-text as *Supplementary Code S00–S14* and available at <https://zenodo.org/records/17476104>.

ID	Description
S00	GenBank feature table extraction.
S01	UniProtKB reference mapping.
S02	Peptide-based physicochemical profiling.
S03	IEDB epitope detection.
S04	PubMed metadata retrieval.
S05	Integration of InterPro, IEDB, PubMed, and UniProtKB data into comprehensive annotations.
S06	Proteome-wide biophysical analysis.
S07	Pangenome ID generation.
S08	SIKU01 PID extraction.
S09	PID locus extraction.
S10	MSA generation for conservation analysis.
S11	Conservation Shannon analysis.
S12	Conservation plotting in ChimeraX.
S13	Epitope localization on PDB structures.
S14	QbD scoring and manufacturability filtering.

Table 13 Each dataset is cited in-text as *Supplementary Data S01–S18* and available at <https://zenodo.org/records/17476104>.

ID	Description
S01	Genome metadata table.
S02	Proteome annotation (GenBank-derived).
S02a	GenBank record of reference strain CP121692.1.
S02b	Extracted protein feature table.
S02c	Predicted proteome (FASTA format).
S02d	Assembled genome (FASTA format).
S03	InterProScan annotations (GFF3 format).
S04	InterProScan annotations (TSV format).
S05	Predicted signal peptide list.
S06	TMHMM-predicted transmembrane helices.
S07	Cytoplasmic antigen candidate list.
S08	KEGG KO annotation table.
S09	KEGG orthology mapping (CSV).
S10	UniProtKB mapping summary (set SF1).
S10a	UniProtKB FASTA dataset for <i>S. iniae</i> (SF1).
S11	DIAMOND reciprocal best-hit mapping results.
S12	UniProtKB keyword annotation list.
S13	UniProtKB keyword mapping for SIKU01 proteins.
S14	Manually curated antigen list.
S15	Physicochemical property matrix of peptides.
S16	IEDB epitope datasets (FASTA + TSV formats).
S17	IEDB– <i>S. iniae</i> homolog cross-reference results.
S18	List of positively predicted antigenic proteins.

Table 14 Each dataset is cited in-text as *Supplementary Data S19–S22* and available at <https://zenodo.org/records/17476104>.

ID	Description
S19	Metadata table for 90 <i>S. iniae</i> isolates.
S20	Pan-genome presence/absence matrices (Roary, Panaroo).
S21	SIKU01 protein identifier (PID) tables.
S22	Shannon entropy and MSA summary results.

Table 15 Each dataset is cited in-text as *Supplementary Data S23–S37* and available at <https://zenodo.org/records/17476104>.

ID	Description
S23	Codon usage frequency table.
S24	Ion-exchange buffer parameters.
S25	QbD M0 manufacturability matrix.
S26	Pre-M1 candidate subset table.
S27	M1 general manufacturability metrics.
S28	M1 protein vaccine matrix.
S29	M1 DNA vaccine matrix (tilapia route).
S30	M1 DNA vaccine matrix (zebrafish route).
S31	M2 anion exchange sub-matrix.
S32	M2 cation exchange sub-matrix.
S33	M2 cellulose affinity sub-matrix.
S34	M2 silica affinity sub-matrix.
S35	M2 DNA vaccine sub-matrix (tilapia).
S36	M2 DNA vaccine sub-matrix (zebrafish).
S37	Final M2 composite manufacturability summary.

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